

Archivists of ‘Feels’:

Web Weaving as Fragmentary Reading
Practice in Tumblr’s Platformized Fan Culture

Chahna Ahuja (r1019982)

Presented in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Arts in Cultural Studies

Supervisor: prof. dr. Jan Baetens

Co-supervisor: Atieh Asadollahi

Academic year 2024-25

27,055 characters

I hereby declare that, in line with the Faculty of Arts' code of conduct for research integrity, the work submitted here is my own original work and that any additional sources of information has been duly cited.

Aspects of popular culture are difficult to understand from a stance of contemplative distance. To understand how popular culture works on our emotions, we have to pull it close, get intimate with it, let it work its magic on us, and then write about our own engagement.

—Henry Jenkins (2007, 10)

Tumblr is a website.

Social network? No, it's a mycelial network.

It's wholesome chaos.

It's the gay people in your phone.

It's your angel. It's your devil.

Tumblr is whatever you want it to be.

Oh, and influencers? Don't even go here. This is your space. Every video you find, every quote you reblog, every tag you curate, every waterfall GIF you secretly gaze at in wonder—that's all you. You're the explorer. We're just a map you all keep on making. Welcome home. Welcome to weird. Make it yours.

#this is not a real post #sorry

69,420 notes

Tumblr, *About*, <https://www.tumblr.com/about> (accessed May 11, 2025).

Acknowledgments

It takes a village to raise a child, and what is this thesis if not my unruly, sleepless, beloved seedling: rooted in the soils of my passion, watered by the patience and guidance of others, and sheltered beneath many caring hands. First and foremost, I express my heartfelt gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Jan Baetens, whose generous guidance and invaluable feedback have profoundly enriched this work. I am equally indebted to my co-supervisor, Atieh Asadollahi, for her enthusiastic encouragement and perceptive insights, which added depth to this study. This thesis tells the story of web weaving as a story of fragments; I, too, am stitched from fragments of tenderness, care, and the utmost patience of those who have held me and witnessed the making of this work. I thank them by weaving their love into a web of gratitude in the form of a When/And-style web weaving post.

When Ada Limón wrote, “I think it’s very dangerous not to have hope. And if you can’t have hope, I think we need a little awe, or a little wonder, or at least a little curiosity,” I thought of my parents, who have filled my life with all the hope, awe, wonder, and curiosity in the world since I was a little girl. I may be a fan of fans, but they have always been my greatest fans. As thankful as I am for their unwavering support, I am also sorry for the squabbles and sadness my stress over this work may have caused them.

When Chen Chen said, “I want to be a village full of sweethearts, as you are, every second of the day,” I heard the laughter of the sweethearts from my village, the friends who carried me through this academic year. Happy, thank you for being my loudest cheerleader, and I will always treasure our walks discussing research methods. Pinar, thanks for being my accomplice through the ‘horrors’ of this thesis. Öykü, you are my favourite hypewoman. Joanne, your sincerity inspires me. Camila, your joyous presence is endlessly infectious. And Sandra, someday I will visit your residence, but you will always be one of the countless people I call home in Leuven.

When Tumblr user @kafk-a posted, “I am not brave but sometimes I am made brave by my friends, which is to say I am made brave by love,” I thought of my beautiful friends whose relentless love makes me brave. Hitaishi, growing up with you means discussing platform cultures and love lives in the mall and oh, how wonderful it is! Tarit, never stop annoying me as a reminder that there is more to life than the walls of my workroom. Deeksha, your encouraging doodle will be treasured whenever I have to fight the big fight. Gowri, sometimes I wonder how I survive, but then I think I survive because I don’t want to stop singing with you yet. Indu, I hope I always make time for you the way you make time for those you love. Mannsi, I am grateful to know I will always find a reader of my work in you. Nat, thank you for spending years of reading in and outside fandoms with me, we will grow old still talking about the ‘blorbos from our shows’.

When I scribbled a verse for Malhar on a cold, snowy thesis morning, “I am a little girl chasing snowflakes as winter howls and bites, but all the girls in me soon will be tired and I’d want the loaves of your arms to keep me warm.” Your arms held me tightly throughout this year. Thanks for listening to my thought spirals, wiping my tears, and calming me down more times than there are pages in this manuscript. Without you, this thesis might have just got stuck on the first chapter. I wish to bask in the earnest warmth and unapologetic dedication of your love throughout my academic endeavours. I promise I will not spend the rest of our lives trying to explain ‘affect’ to you, because ironically, it could never begin to express my ‘feels’ for you.

I am also indebted to KU Leuven’s programme of Cultural Studies for giving me the opportunity to explore my academic interests. Special thanks to Professor Silvana Mandolessi and Professor Benoît Crucifix, whose inspiring classes also influenced the directions of my research.

Lastly, to Tumblr and everyone who calls this hellsite their hellhome.

Abstract

Shining a spotlight on the evolving role of the reader in the digital age, this thesis explores what it means to read in a hyperconnected world where media texts circulate as ‘fragments’ particularly within platformized fan communities. At the heart of this question lies Tumblr’s fragmentary fan reading practice, known as web weaving, both a symptom and a contagion of fragmentary reading and platformized fan culture. In web weaving, users curate fragments—quotes, film stills, lyrics, artworks—into intertextual collages to trace shared emotional themes across seemingly unrelated works. By analyzing the socio-technical infrastructure, platform affordances, and vernacular practices that facilitate web weaving, this thesis conceptualizes Tumblr as a platformed ‘archive of feelings’ (Cvetkovich 2003), where blogs act as public-yet-private databases of media attachments and fan interests. Web weaving emerges as an extension of Tumblr’s affective and archival impulses, preserving fannish ‘feels’ or deeply felt reading experiences. This study argues that web weaving transforms the reader, as a fan, into an archivist who preserves texts that make them feel seen, transformed, and swept away, revealing new contours of knowledge about fragmentary fan reading cultures in communally interpretive yet platformized spaces.

This thesis adopts the sensibility of a ‘methodological bricolage’ (Lindgren 2017), combining multimodal discourse analysis, platform studies-approach, and affect theory in discursive practices to closely read around 80 web weaving posts alongside Tumblr user perspectives on platform culture. Drawing on Lamerichs’ (2022) reception theory of fan affect, Ahmed’s (2004) ‘affective economies’, while also considering Felski’s (2008) modes of textual engagement in reading practices, the study examines affective responses of fans during web weaving to illuminate the relational dynamics between media texts, transformative fandom discourse, and the role of Tumblr as a ‘counterpublic’ platform. Findings suggest that, contrary to scholarly claims of web weaving as a counter-hegemonic practice, web weaving has also fashioned reading as a performance of communal belonging in which readers as fans participate in the logic of value production under platform capitalism, even in seemingly subversive fan cultures. Consequently, the social pressures of fan community norms can delimit affective engagement in web weaving, opening future lines of inquiry into the agency of peer influence in platform cultures and the role of curation in codifying fragmentary reading in the age of digital hyperconnectivity.

Keywords: digital reading practices, fragmentation, platformization, web weaving, Tumblr, digital fan culture, digital hyperconnectivity, archive of feelings, fan affect

Table of Contents

Introduction	1
Chapter 1 Conceptual Convergence of Feeling, Archiving and Reading on Tumblr	6
1.1 Feeling on Tumblr:	6
1.2 Archiving on Tumblr	11
1.3 Reading on Tumblr	15
1.4 Conceptual Focus	20
Chapter 2 Methodologies, Ethics and Research Design	22
2.1 A ‘Bricolage’ of Methodologies	22
2.2 Multimodal Discourse Analysis	23
2.3 Affect as a Multimodal Practice	25
2.4 Data Collection, Ethics and Positionality	27
2.5 Research Questions	29
Chapter 3 Tumblr as Platformed Archive of Feelings	32
3.1 Short History of Tumblr	32
3.2 Platform Structure	34
3.3 Platform Features, Affordances, Vernaculars and Counterpublics	37
3.4 Affective Counterpublics and Their Discontents Under Platform Capitalism	48
3.5 A Bed, A Diary, A Museum: Blogs as ‘Little Databases’	50
3.6 Platformed Archive of Feelings	52
3.7 Archontic Texts in the Tumblr Archive	53
Chapter 4 Web of Fragments: Web Weaving as a Fragmentary Fan Reading Practice	56
4.1 The Fragment, Fragmentary and Fragmentation	56
4.2 Genealogies and Genesis of Web Weaving	58
4.3 Web Weaving as Recognition of the Networked Self	62
4.4 Dwelling in Enchantment: The Aesthetic Experience of Web Weaving	71
4.5 Is Web Weaving a Counter-Hegemonic Knowledge Structure?	77
Conclusion	82
SWOT Analysis	86
Bibliography	88

Table of Figures

Figure 1. Reaction GIFs on Tumblr expressing fannish ‘feels’ 7

Figure 2. ‘Little Digital Archives’ Tumblr post..... 12

Figure 3. Tumblr tags responding to Figure 2, claiming Tumblr as an archive..... 12

Figure 4. Web weaving titled “Dead friendships: There is a hint of tragedy in the neglected corpse that lays between us, one we can never talk about.” 17

Figure 5. Tumblr’s multimodal post options..... 23

Figure 6. Research blog for data collection..... 28

Figure 7. Meme showing Tumblr’s ironic humor about Tumblr's decline..... 34

Figure 8. Tumblr Dashboard: Following, For You, and Your Tags pages..... 35

Figure 9. Trending tags and posts on Tumblr’s Explore (as of 21 July 2025)..... 36

Figures 10.1-10.2. Poll with 712 votes, illustrating skepticism towards Communities..... 37

Figure 11. ‘World War Tea’ post with divergent viewpoints in reblog chains..... 40

Figure 12. Excerpt from a Tumblr instructional post on reblog culture for new users..... 40

Figure 13. Ironic Tumblr textpost about the cyclical nature of reblogging..... 41

Figure 14. Excerpt from an instructional post on Tumblr’s curatorial reblog culture..... 41

Figure 15. Social curation on Tumblr via reblogs..... 42

Figure 16. Tumblr user’s tag directory illustrating curated folksonomies..... 42

Figures 17.1-17.2. User appreciation for Tumblr’s non-searchability and curated tagging..... 43

Figure 18. User discussing Red, White & Royal Blue (2019) book..... 44

Figure 19.1–19.3. User imaginaries of tagging practices..... 45

Figure 20. Vent post featuring personal testimonials..... 45

Figure 21. Tumblr’s multimodal literacies enabled by reblogs..... 46

Figure 22.1. Mockery of algorithmic design of platforms..... 47

Figure 22.2. User expressing distaste for ‘For You’ page..... 47

Figure 22.3: Users discuss Tumblr’s anti-clout and anti-influencer culture..... 47

Figure 23. User critique of moral policing for liking ‘problematic’ characters..... 48

Figure 24. ‘Media Literacy is dying!’ weaponized for pathologizing fans of color..... 49

Figures 25.1-25.7. The shared imaginary of Tumblr as an archival space..... 52

Figure 26. Moodboard for Barbatos from the video game Genshin Impact (2020)..... 59

Figure 27. Ink and Pa (queer characters) GIF set from Bad Buddy (2021)..... 59

Figure 28. Part of Bad Buddy (2021) text post memes compilation..... 60

Figure 29. A web weaving titled : “it says, “stay”, dad”..... 64

Figure 30.1. A web weaving for The Bear (2022): “Michael & Natalie Berzatto”..... 67

Figure 30.2. A user’s response to The Bear (2022) web weaving..... 67

Figure 31.1: A web weaving titled, “there’s so much love in the world. so much love you could drown in it..... 70

Figure 31.2: Corresponding tags on the above web weaving/..... 71

Figure 31.3: Reblogged comment by a user on the above web weaving/..... 71

Figures 32.1-32.2. User experience of web weaving as magic and alchemy..... 72

Figure 33. When/And collaborative web weaving post..... 73

Figures 34.1-34.2: Users on juxtaposition of high and popular culture in web weaving..... 75

Figure 35. Web weaving post referencing Van Gogh, Susan Sontag, children’s book, and contemporary poetry..... 76

Figure 36. Literary ‘canons’ in web weaving..... 78

Figure 37. Tumblr’s ‘common literary language’ 79

Figure 38. Favourite literary fragments of users..... 79

Figure 39. Growing anxieties around authenticity of reception in web weaving..... 80

Figure 40. Critique of decontextualization in fragmentary reading..... 80

Figures 41.1-41.2. Users frustrated over decontextualization of quotes..... 81

Figures 42.1-42.2. Users distaste for rise of web weaving on Instagram and TikTok..... 85

Introduction

Who knows, maybe one day there will no longer be Literature. Instead there will be literary web sites. Like those stars, still shining but long dead, the web sites will testify to the existence of past writers. There will be quotes, fragments of texts, which prove that there used to be complete texts once. Instead of readers there will be cyber space travelers who will stumble upon the websites by chance and stop for a moment to gaze at them. How will they read them? — Dubravka Ugrešić (n.d.)¹

A monk etches into a wax tablet, reading slowly as his stylus moves through softened clay. A scroll is unfurled and read aloud to a hushed, encircled crowd. A teenage girl clutches a paperback beneath her covers, leaning toward the glow of a night lamp to follow the words. A user scrolls endlessly through flickering screens, reading curated content on social media platforms.

The history of reading is, in many ways, the history of changing technologies. And it is a truth—if not universally, then increasingly acknowledged in literary and cultural studies—that reading has fundamentally changed in the digital age. Engaging more closely with this claim often leads one into a rabbit hole of scholarship on digital reading culture. These studies reveal that abstract cause-and-effect discussions on whether the digital changes culture are no longer sufficient or particularly illuminating.

What is perhaps more interesting is turning to detailed analyses of specific cultural phenomena that show how the multifaceted impacts of the digital have transformed the cultural experiences and practices of reading. These include, but are not limited to: the rise of “bookishness”, or the digital performance of a self aligned with books (Pressman 2020); the emergence of social reading and participatory literary cultures on platforms like Bookstagram and BookTok² (Birke 2021); the blurring of high and popular literary culture through celebrity book clubs, online bookstores, film adaptations, and social book cataloguing and reviewing platforms like Goodreads (Collins 2010; Birke & Fehrle 2019); the proliferation of digital fandoms on social media that discuss media texts (Booth 2017); and the increasing fragmentation of attention in response to the ceaseless availability of media texts as ‘content’ (Gómez et al. 2021). These cultural shifts raise crucial questions about the increasingly fragmentary and platformized nature of contemporary reading practices that can be contemplated as consequences of digital hyperconnectivity.

¹ This is a quote from the website’s homepage of the writer, Dubravka Ugrešić.

² Bookstagram and BookTok are colloquial terms for thriving online bookish communities that center around books, reading, literary discussions and the experience of being a reader.

Rogers Brubaker (2023), in *Hyperconnectivity and its Discontents*, defines hyperconnectivity as the condition of being constantly connected to everything and everyone through the digital realm. It has restructured attention, reconfigured social relations into platform-friendly, surveillance-enhancing forms, transformed our experience of space and time, and converted human culture into a continuous stream of algorithmically delivered digital content. (Brubaker 2023, 2). The ‘hyper’ in hyperconnectivity thus signals not only constant connectivity mediated by digital platforms but also the collapse of temporal and spatial linearity in how we experience information. The state of being perpetually online to consume the overabundance of media texts (books, movies, memes, social media posts, celebrities, and games) has made “reading on the web a short, fragmented, nomadic activity, in which the reader surfs from one hyperlink to another in the order of his/her choice” (Bouchardon 2019). In contrast to immersive linear reading experiences of print media, fragmentary reading refers to the ways of engaging with media texts in a non-linear, disjointed, and selective manner due to media abundance in digital hyperconnectivity. Platform infrastructures in the age of digital hyperconnectivity have offered possibilities for micro-communication content (blog posts, memes, tweets, and short-form video content) to gain cultural prominence, further contributing to the rise of fragmentary reading practices.

In this sense, platformization of media texts is another defining condition of reading practices in the digital age. Borrowing from scholars, such as Nieborg and Poell (2018, 2019), I refer to platformization as “the reorganization of cultural practices and imaginations around platforms” (Poell et al. 2019, 6). That is, platforms have become sites for the production, distribution, and circulation of cultural texts. Their notion of platformization also focuses on how the profit motives of platforms lead organizations to design and govern platform infrastructures that best exercise their commercial interests. Platformization, then, is not just a technological condition; it is also a cultural and economic consequence of digital hyperconnectivity.

According to Brubaker, platformization has deeply impacted amateur cultural creativity found in online media fandoms: “[The] expansive terrains of amateur cultural production and circulation in which many users share their own creations—photos, fanfiction, poetry, music, videos, commentary, and so forth—... have become deeply embedded in a commercial ecosystem of tightly interconnected digital platforms” (Brubaker 2023, 88). Fan practices, once considered as resistant or oppositional forms of reading, are becoming increasingly mainstream under platform capitalism. This is clearly evident in the rise of platformed fan communities across TikTok, X, Instagram, Tumblr, Reddit, Discord, and beyond.

Within platformized cultural production, digital fan communities actively shape contemporary reading practices. I define fan reading as a social practice in which fans claim

the right to publish their own interpretations of source texts, often expanding their engagement with the source text through fanfiction, fan art, memes, edits, and discourse. These transformative fanworks critique, reinterpret, or reject aspects of the ‘canon’—“the events presented in the media source that provide the universe, setting, and characters for fanworks” (Busse and Hellekson 9)—or the authorial storyworld fans take as a starting point for their creative labour. Yet as fans play with these authorial meanings, media industries under platform capitalism also play with them by commodifying their engagements. Platform infrastructures and the communal expectations of fandom enable and simultaneously delimit how transformative readings are performed, shared, circulated, and consumed. It raises critical questions about the nature of transformative fan creativity, steered by the implicit cultural expectations of organized platformed fan communities and the technosocial infrastructures that profit from these communities.

I posit fragmentation and platformization as acute symptoms of digital hyperconnectivity that have transformed the way readers read, interpret, and circulate media texts. My thesis centers on digital fan cultures, because nowhere more vividly can we witness the nature of reading practices than among fans due to the contemporary overabundance of fan content and platformization of fan communities. The primary purpose of my thesis is to explore the fragmentation and platformization of digital reading practices through the case study of Tumblr’s web weaving. I consider web weaving as a fan reading practice that both reflects and responds to the fragmented, platformized conditions of reading in digital culture.

Web weaving is a practice that emerged on Tumblr around 2018. In this practice, Tumblr users weave together disparate fragments of media texts—literary quotes, film and TV stills, song lyrics, artworks, and social media posts—into a curated web to trace thematic emotional threads across these texts. To the best of my knowledge, there is little sustained research on web weaving thus far. This is not astonishing considering the mainstream decline of Tumblr in both popular imagination and cultural research of this decade. Web weaving occupies part of Ester Frieder’s *I am like a pdf but a girl: Girlblogging as a nomadic pedagogy* (2025), examining counter-hegemonic knowledge practices on Tumblr amongst girlbloggers who are marginalized Tumblr users with female and queer subjectivities. I am indebted to the work of Axel-Nathaniel Rose (2023, 2024, 2025) on parallel posts (an interchangeable term for web weaving), who in his doctoral dissertation, *#parallels: Web Weaving, Media Fandom, and the Role of Bookishness on Tumblr* analyzes the poetics of the practice to understand Tumblr’s literary culture. In his study, Rose (2025) asks a pressing question, “What does it mean to be a ‘reader’ in an age of digital hyperconnectivity?” I take his query a step further by explicitly situating web weaving as a fragmentary reading practice within Tumblr’s platformed fan culture.

At the heart of my research lies the question: *What does it mean to be a reader in a hyperconnected yet fragmented digital world characterized by platformization of fan culture?*

With this question in mind, I analyze the platform infrastructure and fan culture of Tumblr that together made possible the emergence of web weaving. I theorize Tumblr blogs as platformed ‘archives of feelings’, curating media attachments while enabling the reinterpretation and reauthoring of media texts through transformative fan practices. In this light, web weaving emerges as an extension of Tumblr’s archival and transformative impulses. Web weaving preserves the traces of feelings evoked by media texts and shares interpretive fan reading experiences by weaving disconnected fragments of media texts into intertextual dialogue with one another, curating webs of feelings rooted in fan reception.

I argue that web weaving transforms the reader as a fan into an archivist who preserves reading experiences that make them feel seen, transformed, and swept away within the archival environment of blogs, bringing into view new contours of knowledge about fragmentary fan reading cultures in communally interpretive yet platformized fandom spaces. At the same time, this act of archiving exists in a space between the interpretive experiences of fans and the restrictions within platformized fan communities that have developed their own norms and cultural expectations. To understand web weaving as a Tumblr fragmentary fan reading practice is to gain insights into Tumblr’s platform architecture, affordances/constraints, user communication practices and the transformative mode of media engagements. These insights reveal how readers as fans fashion themselves in ways to perform belonging in platformized fan communities and participate in the logic of value production under platform capitalism, even within seemingly subversive fan spaces. I study web weaving as an exemplar of what it means to experience media and express those reading experiences in a fragmented, platformized and hyperconnected digital world.

Each chapter of the thesis begins with an epigraph of a literary fragment that threads the chapter’s theme because web weaving is, after all, a story told in fragments. The structure of the thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces relevant conceptual terms guiding this work. I briefly acquaint readers with Tumblr’s quintessential ‘culture of feels,’ where intensely felt reading experiences become performances of shared emotions within fan communities. The chapter accentuates the central role of affect in fan reception on Tumblr, reviewing literature from the ‘affective turn’ in fan studies. I establish that performance, curation and circulation of reading experiences through fan practices position Tumblr as a platformed archive of feelings. Web weaving is introduced as a one such fan reading practice where feeling, reading, and archiving converge in media reception of fans within the fragmented, multimodal, platformized environment of digital reading culture.

Chapter 2 explains the methodological underpinnings of this study. I borrowed Lindgren’s model of a ‘methodological bricolage’ as a label for my method. It combines multimodal discourse analysis, a platform studies approach, and affect theory in discursive practices (Berg et al. 2019) to examine the relationship between Tumblr’s platform architecture, user experiences, and participatory fan culture and web weaving as a cultural practice. I also explain my data collection process, ethical considerations, and positionality, which are closely intertwined in the research design. Furthermore, I elaborate on how the research questions inform the upcoming analysis chapters.

Chapter 3 opens with a brief history of Tumblr, discussing how a platform often deemed ‘dead’ has sustained fan communities for nearly two decades. It examines how Tumblr’s architecture fosters affordances and constraints in the eyes of users who have developed vernacular practices that have cultivated ‘counterpublic’ subcultures around fandom, queerness, art, writing, mental health, and social justice that both Tumblr users and various scholars read as counter-hegemonic. By questioning its counter-hegemonic status, I analyze how the platform infrastructure and fan culture have made certain kinds of fan emotions a cultural currency for participating in Tumblr fandoms, which consequently generates value for the platform. I also note that Tumblr is an anomaly, as limited automation and user resistance to algorithmic governance have slowed the extractivism of platform capitalism. The chapter also considers Tumblr as a social curatorial space where blogs are users’ ‘little databases’ for preserving content that holds affective significance to them, which further substantiates Tumblr’s function as a platformed ‘archive of feelings’. Tumblr’s affective and archival environment enables users to treat media texts as repositories for redeploying content in their fan creations, a feature central to web weaving’s fragmentary form.

Chapter 4 situates web weaving within a genealogy of fragmentary collage forms and earlier Tumblr practices, tracing its roots in the platform’s quotation culture. The chapter closely reads selected web weaving posts, examining how the practice enables users to feel seen in the polyphonic echoes of others, captivates them through the fragmentary nature of reading that encourages an outpouring of poetic expression, and instils knowledge about the sprawling sociality of platformized fan culture. It also considers whether affective responses are deeply personal or strategically performed for visibility within affective fandom economies under platform capitalism.

The conclusion summarizes my analysis and outlines the limitations and future directions of the research.

Chapter 1 Conceptual Convergence of Feeling, Archiving and Reading on Tumblr

I migrated sharing my personal “feels” and obsessions from music forums and sites like LiveJournal to posting diary-like fragments on tumblr. Those first posts are gone, manually deleted, but others endure. Each new blog marked a new project: excerpts from literature I loved, frustrated rants about the hardcore punk scene I was sort of in, screenshots of text conversations that were just too personal to go elsewhere. Like the boxes of letters, photos, and other personal archives under my bed, tumblr curates my passions and transformations. — Natalia Ann Hendry (Tiidenberg et al. 2021, 12)

1.1 Feeling on Tumblr:

1.1.1 ‘Feels’ and Pleasures of Fandom

“That hit me right in the feels”, “Send help! I am drowning in feels”, “I have a lot of feels for them”, “#my feels”, “#fandom feels”: If you have ever been part of Tumblr fan culture, you might recognize ‘feels’ as those looping reaction GIFs of characters wailing, screaming, tearfully admitting their feelings. These GIFs (Figure 1) are a performative way for fans to publicly dramatize the overwhelming pleasures and intensities unleashed by the media texts they read. For those unfamiliar with the social blogging platform Tumblr or its fan culture— don’t worry, this chapter aims to get you acquainted— ‘feels’ is shorthand for feelings. But the way it has been used in digital fan communities differs qualitatively from the everyday use of ‘feelings’. As Mithen puts it in their provocatively titled essay “In Defense of Feels”: “‘Feels’ are reserved for feelings related to the experience of fannish pleasure—in my experience, with an overtone of a subset of extremely intense feelings that we all understand are linked to a fictional artifact” (Mithen 2014). ‘Feels’ as a fannish term emerged in digital fan communities to evoke the presence of intensely felt experiences of fans towards their media interests.

Figure 1. [Reaction GIFs](#) on Tumblr expressing fannish ‘feels’.³

‘Feels’, as a conceptual metaphor, represents the pivotal movement from private reception to public expression. When a media text powerfully draws a reader into its world, takes them down new perceptual or interpretive paths and affects them in unanticipated ways, the resulting intensity of reception becomes an irresistible urge to share for many readers. It propels readers to discuss their readerly experiences with others and even create creative works—be it reaction GIFs, memes, fanfiction, fanart—to process and extend their very attachments with the media texts. While readers have always sought out participatory experiences and fan spaces since the advent of print culture, digital platforms have exponentially expanded the scale and speed at which this occurs. The platformization of fan communities has made it possible for fans to connect with others who not only share their fannish interests but also recognize the powerful, all-consuming potency of ‘feels’ in reading experiences.

Tumblr holds a unique place within today’s platformized fandom landscape. Unlike mainstream platforms such as Instagram, YouTube, or TikTok, often associated with commercialized fan content and aggressive algorithmic models, Tumblr is perceived by fans

³ Top Left- *No Face* from *Spirited Away* adrift in ‘feels’, Top Right- Kristen Wiig in *Bridesmaids* saying, “I just have a lot of feelings”, Middle Left- *Jake the Dog* from *Adventure Time* wailing, Middle Left - Will Ferrell in *Anchorman* screaming, “I am in a glass case of emotion!”, Bottom Left- Captain America from *Marvel Cinematic Universe* being hit by an explosion of ‘feels’, Bottom Right- Donald Glover in *Community* crying in a theatre seat, shouting, “My emotions! My emotions!”

as more niche or ‘non-mainstream’ in current times. As shall be seen, Tumblr does not fully conform to the dominant algorithmic ad-driven platform model that defines the condition of platform capitalism today. Nevertheless, Tumblr still capitalizes from its user base being so passionate about their media attachments to capture user attention, which is why it becomes pertinent to study the performance and circulation of ‘feels’ in reading practices of fans.

This chapter begins with Tumblr’s ‘culture of feels’ to recognize the fannish intensities in Tumblr fan activities and practices that are derived from performing and circulating ‘feels’. It foregrounds the role of affect in fan reception and hints at how Tumblr’s affective economies profit from fan engagement as a consequence of platform capitalism. I seek to establish how the curation and circulation of ‘feels’ through fan practices positions Tumblr for its users as a digital archive of feelings. I will then situate one native Tumblr fan practice, web weaving, as a case study that serves as an entry point to analyze how feeling, archiving and reading on Tumblr converge in response to the fragmented, multimodal and platformized condition of reading in the digital age.

1.1.2 Tumblr's 'Culture of Feels' and Affective Reception

Since its inception in 2007, Tumblr has been considered a subcultural digital platform by its fan communities. McCracken et al. (2020), in their book *a tumblr book: platform and cultures* evocatively describe this subcultural ecology of the platform: “Tumblr was, for many, a deinstitutionalized, underfunded, unauthorized, constantly on-the-run think tank–cum–chocolate factory, a subcultural, countercultural place where alternative pleasures, education and resource-sharing, creative and critical work happened” (2020, 3). The authors contend that Tumblr’s pseudonymous and non-linear reblogging architecture, liberal demographics and marginal status outside the mainstream social media limelight have made the platform an alternative world for users who are often marginalized in the public sphere. Tumblr offers a digital environment for these users to explore their alternative pleasures by coming together over mutual passions, cultivating what Stein (2015) calls as ‘culture of feels’: “Emotions remain intimate but are no longer necessarily private; rather, they build a sense of an intimate collective, one that is bound together precisely by the processes of shared emotional authorship ... [fuel]ling fan transformative creativity, and performances of shared emotion [that] define fan authorship communities” (Stein 2015, 156).

Fan studies scholar Nicolle Lamerichs (2018) builds on Stein’s ‘culture of feels’ to emphasize affect as central to fan identity on Tumblr, “which is grounded in an emotional ownership of media content” (19). ‘Feels’ culture captures how private reception of fans moves to collective fan discourses because readers begin to feel a personal stake in the media text that they need to share with others. This emotional investment is then not just expressive, but reflexive, which allows fans to treat the media text as something they can claim, interpret and even transform based on their desires and interpretations. Tumblr’s platform architecture

and affordances open up imaginative possibilities for fans to collaboratively and collectively play with their source media texts by contextualizing, recontextualizing, transforming, subverting, or even rejecting their canonical (as is used in fan culture) meanings through transformative practices of fanfiction, fanart, memes, reaction GIFs, cosplay, fan edits, and other discursive activities.

Lamerichs (2018) theorizes the performance of ‘feels’ through fan practices as a mode of fan reception called ‘affective reception’. Unlike many prior works in fan studies where affect is invoked loosely or incidentally, Lamerichs offers a scholarly engagement with the ‘affective turn’ in fan studies. She critically revisits earlier approaches to affect in fan studies, such as Matt Hills’ (2001) idea of fandom as ‘affective spaces’ and Lawrence Grossberg’s (1992) ‘mattering maps.’ Hills draws on Benedict Anderson’s ‘imagined communities’ (1983) to suggest that fandom is an affective space constructed by members who imagine themselves as part of a socially constructed community based on a shared affinity. Grossberg, on the other hand, offers a more granular framework for how fans assign intensity and significance to cultural texts. His notion of ‘mattering maps’ charts the intensities through which people invest in particular texts, identities, or issues at different moments in their lives. Lamerichs extends this idea by showing how characters become crucial sites of affective reception within the mattering maps of fans as their intensities toward these characters evolve. For instance, a character who once elicited strong feelings in childhood may no longer resonate in adulthood. But her main contribution to the ‘affective turn’ is the grounding of affect in reception theory. Moving beyond the structuralist models like Greimas’ (1993) ‘semiotics of passions,’ where the locus of passions—mental states of thoughts, feelings and behavioural responses with a degree of intensity—to produce meaning in a text lies in the internal structures of text, Lamerichs shifts the focus to the passions of the reader.

In the complex field of the ‘affective turn,’ the term ‘affect’ carries multiple meanings. For the purpose of this project, my use of ‘affect’ is grounded in Nicolle Lamerichs’s reception theory. She defines affect as “a flow of feelings that audiences experience as they process a narrative” (Lamerichs and Rosendo 2022, 200). She traces ontological (Massumi 2002), socially constructed (Gomart and Hennion 1999), and embodied (Sobchak 2004) theories of affect, but focuses instead on a reception-oriented framework that brings these schools of thought into conversation with one another: “Affective reception as a process in which emotions are crucial but not fixed” (Lamerichs and Rosendo 2022, 200). Unlike the Deleuzian idea of affect as a pre-personal intensity, Lamerichs does not exclude the discursivity of emotions in her reception theory of affect. In her model of affective reception, “emotions are not separate from affect but can be understood as its aftermath, an aftermath that is especially important within fandom because affect is reiterated consciously and productively” (Lamerichs 2018, 207). In other words, affective reception is the interpretive process where the visceral intensities of fans towards media texts are consciously

engaged and productively materialized into emotions through fan discourses. ‘Feels’ are performed and productively articulated through various emotional responses to media texts using fan practices.

There is a necessary dynamic continuum between affect and affective reception: affect is the potential of strong, intense attachments towards media texts, while affective reception is the active process through which this potential becomes socially meaningful and culturally materialized within fandom through discursive fan activities that showcase the affective reading experiences of fans. Thus, affect is part of a hermeneutic process for fans. In this regard, she also states that “fans are deeply engaged with popular content that leads to specific structures of close reading and emotional forms of reception” (2018, 19). This research project takes Lamerichs’ insight as a point of departure to understand how ‘feels’ as affect is central to Tumblr fandoms. ‘Feels’ have ushered in specific modes of reading and emotional forms of reception, which is visible in web weaving as a fragmentary fan reading practice driven by affective reception of fans across Tumblr fan communities.

1.1.3 Affective Economies of Platformized Fan Culture

Lamerichs helps us understand how fans perform ‘feels’, but it does not fully address how affective reception of fans circulates and gains traction across fan communities networks on Tumblr. This is an important consideration to understand Tumblr’s ‘culture of feels’ that builds an intimate collective of fans. I turn to Sara Ahmed’s theory of ‘affective economies’, which shifts the focus from emotion as interpretation to emotion as circulation. Ahmed argues that “in such affective economies, emotions do things, and they align individuals with communities ... by sticking figures together (adherence), a sticking that creates the very effect of a collective (coherence)” (2004, 119). This explains how ‘feels’ travel beyond individual fans to produce shared emotional authorship. In Tumblr’s affective fan economies, emotions circulate through reblogs, tags, and pseudonymous blogs that facilitate a highly multimodal, curatorial, non-linear and interactive environment. ‘Feels’ ‘stick’ to shared media texts and gain meaning as they are amplified and responded to by others through a visibly stylized platform vernacular, culturally specific and user-developed modes of expression that we see across Tumblr.

The affective economies of Tumblr reveal how social media platforms are designed to elicit, capture, and monetize user emotions. In forthcoming chapters, I will demonstrate how Tumblr has long struggled to establish a stable monetization model; yet it stays afloat because of users’ affective engagements with media, with fan communities playing a very active role in engaging with its peculiar interface. As mentioned earlier, Tumblr is often perceived as a ‘counter-hegemonic’ space by its marginalized queer, feminist and fan userbase who perform and archive their interests and fannish pleasures in their Tumblr blogs (Frieder 2025, 35). Is Tumblr truly as counter-hegemonic as it appears at first glance?

The Gramscian sense of hegemony used here refers to the dominance of the media industry in setting the terms of cultural legitimacy in contrast to fanish work. The tension between Tumblr fandom’s implicit resistance to capitalism and its explicit tethering to platformed fan cultures already indicates the eclecticism of Tumblr’s transformational fan practices. Unlike more overtly commercial platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, or TikTok, Tumblr may function as a counterpublic space and attract marginalized fan communities (queer, neurodivergent, or racialized users) but these conditions alone do not inherently make Tumblr a site of resistance. I hesitate to label Tumblr as ‘counter-hegemonic’ because Tumblr’s platform architecture, affordances, and broader vernacular of platformed participation simultaneously enable but also constrain how fans are expected to express media attachments. In this study, I examine how the affective economies of Tumblr inform the practice of web weaving: do Tumblr users reflect their sincere affective reception in this reading practice, or is it governed by implicit norms of how fans are expected to feel a certain way about certain media texts, aligning with what the platform or fan communities tend to reward and amplify. These expectations often centre Anglophone content as cultural capital and white, North American queer subjectivities, thereby reproducing dominant hierarchies of race, region, and queerness, even within seemingly subversive platformed fan culture of Tumblr. Certain forms of affective reception or ‘feels’ become more visible, validated and legible within the ‘intimate collectives’ of fan communities. As a result, even if Tumblr is perceived as counter-hegemonic by users, the ongoing circulation of ‘feels’ influenced by the platform architecture and affective economies of Tumblr raises questions about the sincere performance of ‘feels’ that users wish to preserve in their blogs.

1.2 Archiving on Tumblr

1.2.1 From Blogs to Little Databases

Shared emotional authorship of media texts is the defining state of Tumblr’s ‘culture of feels’. Stein (2015) characterizes shared emotional authorship as a quality of the Tumblr blog. She cites Paul Booth (2017), who argues in *Digital Fandom* that “a blog post is not only authored by the person who originally wrote or constructed the post, but also by all the others who come along and add comments and conversation” (Stein 2015, 157). The primary interaction mechanism on Tumblr is the reblogging feature that allows users to repost other users’ content on their own blog with the option to add commentary. The act of reblogging lends itself to the decentered notion of authorship. It stimulates the circulation of varied interests, tastes, and affective reception of countless media texts through multiple community clusters, shifting the tone and content with each reblog as each user interprets content based on their emotions and interest affinities. By reframing content for their own interests in their blogs, the act of reblogging allows Tumblr users to discover, select, catalogue, interpret, share, and preserve content. This content also includes fan practices such as memes, fanart,

web weaving and fan discourse. In this way, shared emotional authorship manifests through the curatorial performance of blogging.

Although the platform features of Tumblr are not designed to make it a curatorial platform in comparison to say Pinterest, reblogging has enabled users to participate in what Tiidenberg et al. (2021), in their book *tumblr*, call ‘social curation’: “A blog can be a tightly curated performance, or a loosely curated collection of stuff that might have nothing more in common than that it was all selected, framed, and shared by one person” (2021, 58). Social curation has led to a popular user imagination of Tumblr as an ‘archive’. In Frieder’s survey (2021), many respondents described their blogging experiences using metaphors of curation:

The comparison to Tumblr blogging as either a diary/journal or as a museum space was very prevalent: several responders directly referred to bloggers as “curators” rather than artists. They saw themselves as mediators and organizers of their personalized space, customized just for their enjoyment. Other metaphors were to a bedroom, a home, and a treasure box. (Frieder 2021, 10)

The popular imagination of Tumblr as an archival site comes alive in this widely circulated 2023 Tumblr post: (Figure 2), where users engaged with this post through reblogs to position their blogs as “little digital archives” in the tags (Figure 3). I want to take a closer look at the invocation of the word ‘little’ here through Snelson’s (2025) concept of the ‘little database’.

girls love having their little digital archives

Figure 2. ‘Little Digital Archives’ Tumblr post.

#this is what my tumblr is to me #tumblr in a nutshell
 #I'm the archivist of my favorite silly posts
 #why do you think I'm so fixated on this inconsequential little blog? #tumblr is my diary
 #reasons why tumblr remains my social media platform of choice
 #by far the best archive filtering features
 #it's true! #i love my tumblr #me with this blog tbh
 #why i'll never leave tumblr tbh #that's why i tag everything in such detail #much. archive.

Figure 3. Tumblr tags responding to Figure 2, claiming Tumblr as an archive.

Drawing upon the analogy of German avant-garde ‘little magazines’ that were experimental, underground publications that challenged commercial publishing norms, Snelson understands ‘little databases’ not just as small databases but as grassroots, experimental archival projects whose archival logics are indeed committed to preservation

and access. But the structure of this archival form “inhabits[s] the vexed space between preservation and distribution, between memory and practice” (Snelson 2025, 7). The nature of the ‘little database’ within the digital archival ecosystem disrupts the binary between archiving and circulation by unsettling conventional relationships between cultural memory and media objects. From my perspective, these personal user blogs function as ‘little databases’ where media objects are not fixed storage units of data, but continuously reconfigured through acts of selection, tagging, and reblogging. This curatorial performance gestures toward what Mandolessi (2023), borrowing from Hayles (2007), has described “as the symbiosis between database and narrative, where the database emerges as a cultural form that incorporates narrative elements” (1519). In this ‘little database’ of user blogs, meaning does not arise solely from the socio-technical practice of storing media objects as data, but from the interpretive relationships users form with them by curating media objects for their own narrative, that is, for their own blog. As a digital fan culture platform, these narratives revolve around the alternative pleasures of users as fans of media texts, which are, of course, often materially discarded in ‘big’ institutional archives. This understanding of Tumblr blogs as ‘little databases’ where users curate and preserve content that holds affective significance for them allows me to engage with Cvetkovich (2003) to conceptualize the functioning of Tumblr as a digital archive of feelings.

1.2.2 Tumblr and Archive of Feelings

In *An Archive of Feelings*, Ann Cvetkovich (2003) makes a strong case for the importance of the emotional effects of archives. She discusses lesbian and gay archives to suggest that “lesbian and gay history demands a radical archive of emotion in order to document intimacy, sexuality, love, and activism—all areas of experience that are difficult to chronicle through the materials of a traditional archive” (Cvetkovich 2003, 241). Similar to Snelson’s examples of the non-institutional initiatives of the ‘little databases’, these archives as repositories of queer feelings that document the marginalized lived experiences of queer people are often neglected within dominant institutional hierarchies of archival systems. Cvetkovich also expands the definition of the archive beyond institutional brick-and-mortar archives like the *Lesbian Herstory Archives* to include multi-sited cultural texts and archival practices charged with affect. ‘Archives of feelings’, she writes, are “repositories of feelings and emotions, which are encoded not only in the content of the texts themselves but in the practices that surround their production and reception” (7). On Tumblr, reblogging and tagging enable users to curate, circulate, and preserve media texts in their personal micro-archives or ‘little databases’ of blogs. These communication practices will help me consider how Tumblr’s platform affordances and culture build the ontology of Tumblr as a platformed archive of feelings.

1.2.3 *Media Texts as Archives*

Abigail De Kosnik, in her seminal work, *Rogue Archives: Digital Cultural Memory and Media Fandom* (2016), analyzes how Cvetkovich aligns queer archiving with fan archiving by discussing fan reception in queer communities. Cvetkovich writes, “I take the fan as a model for the archivist. The archivist of queer culture must proceed like the fan or the collector whose attachment to objects is often fetishistic, idiosyncratic, or obsessional” (Cvetkovich 2003, 253). The terms ‘fetishistic’, ‘idiosyncratic’, or ‘obsessional’ bring to light the intensities of affective labour in fan practices that produce ‘feels’. Although expressed differently, Cvetkovich explicitly views fans as archivists who preserve their affective reception of media texts through fan practices. “The fan cultures that queer certain stars or the use of pulp novels as an indication of the existence of homosexuality are historical practices whose story is not wholly told by the objects and persons in and around which these forms of reception take place. ... In the archive of lesbian feeling, objects are not inherently meaningful but are made so through their significance to an audience” (Cvetkovich 2003, 254). ‘Archive of feelings’ confronts that meaning in source texts is not intrinsic, but produced by the audience’s interpretive practices based on their affective reception of media texts. This ethos of ‘archive of feelings’, where fans are a model for archivists, holds a profound theoretical foundation for my thesis.

De Kosnik builds upon Cvetkovich’s notion of fans as archivists by analyzing grassroots fan archives like Archive of Our Own that are created and managed by the archival labour of fans. The contemporary world of digital hyperconnectivity has given rise to the new economy of attention. This attention economy constitutes an abundance of communicative and mediated experiences that can be viewed as what De Kosnik calls as ‘archontic productions’. ‘Archontic’ is a term De Kosnik derives from Derrida’s *Archive Fever* (1995), in which he claims that archives are never completely finished and always open to preserve new materials. He calls the continuous expansion of the archive that constantly gathers, unifies, classifies and adds more material to enlarge itself as the ‘archontic principle’. Reframing this ‘archontic principle’ to understand digital media productions generated by fan practices and fan activities, De Kosnik discusses her theory of ‘archontic productions’. She calls the readers of media texts as users of digital culture; these users see the vast collection of media texts as an archive of source materials for their own creations: “From this archive of source texts, media users select the texts they want to work with, and from those texts, they extract what they like and what they need, using those extractions as the raw materials for their own cultural productions, such as fan fiction” (De Kosnik 2016, 54). This thesis characterizes the curatorial practice of web weaving as a contemporary and academically understudied form of archontic production within Tumblr’s digital archive of feelings.

1.3 Reading on Tumblr

1.3.1 *What is Web Weaving?*

In simple terms, web weaving is a Tumblr practice of bringing together fragments of texts, quotes, poetry, song lyrics, artworks, GIFs, and stills from films and TV into a unifying narrative. The purpose of placing the collected fragments in dialogue with one another is to curate a thematic parallel, a shared emotional thread woven by users based on their reception of these texts. This is why they are also referred to as parallel posts. The most prevalent format of this practice involves vertically arranging images of fragments, often with a title that thematizes the web weave along with citations of all sources at the end of the post in chronological order.

Figure 4 is an example of a web weave. It is titled: “Dead friendships: There is a hint of tragedy in the neglected corpse that lays between us, one we can never talk about” and includes a list of citations that correspond to the order of the texts used. It also includes the sources in the tags along with tags like #web weaving #parallels #quotes that users use to catalogue this fan practice on Tumblr. Rose’s work (2023, 2024, 2025) will remain as my primary scholarly reference for understanding web weaving as a Tumblr practice. Rose states that “web weaving emerged from the intersection of bookish and fandom communities now known as Dark Academia in approximately 2018” (Rose 2024). To understand this fragmentary form at the intersection of bookish and fannish communities, I will return to these origins of web weaving in Chapter 4 by situating the practice within broader cultures of fragmentary forms that Gowrley (2024) explores in her eponymous book. I will also trace the roots of web weaving in other fragmentary fan reading practices of Tumblr fan cultures.

Girls love each other like animals. There is something ferocious and unself-conscious about it. We don't guard ourselves like we do with boys. No one trains us to shield our hearts from each other. With girls, it's total vulnerability from the beginning. Our skin is bare and soft. We love with claws and teeth and the blood is just proof of how much. It's feral.

And it's relentless.

I forget the reason, but I loved you once, remember?

I wanted to hurt you
 but the victory is that I could not stomach it.

And autumn comes when you're not yet done
 With the summer passing by, but
 I don't think I could stand to be
 Where you don't see me

What exists between us
 is like a wounded beast
 that doesn't recover and
 doesn't die.

What we share, [he] and I, may be a lot like a traffic accident, but we do share it. We are survivors, of each other. We have been shak to one another, but also lifboat. That counts for something.

I no longer love her, that's certain, but maybe I love her.
Love is so short, forgetting is so long.

You're going to die
in your best friend's arms.
And you play along because it's funny, because it's written down,
you've memorized it,
it's all you know.

Friendship plants itself as a small unobtrusive seed; over time, it grows thick roots that wrap around your heart. When a love affair ends, the tree is torn out quickly, the operation painful but clean. Friendship withers quietly, there is always hope of revival. Only after time has passed do you recognise that it is dead, and you are left, for years afterwards, pulling dry brown fibres from your chest.

Now that I'm free to be myself, who am I?

Dead friendships: There is a hint of tragedy in the neglected corpse that lays between us, one we can never talk about.

Leah Raedar// The Social Network dir. David Fincher// Sandra Cisneros// Sylvia Plath//Richard Siken//Mitski// Ahmed Al-Mulla// Margaret Atwood//Pablo Neruda// Fleabag// Richard Siken// Anna Lyndsey// Thoroughbreds dir. Cory Finley// Mary Oliver

#dead friendships #broken friendship #friendship #richard siken #mitski #anna taylor joy #thoroughbreds #david fincher #the social network #Mary Oliver #Ahmed Al-Mulla #Saudi poets #sandra cisneros #pablo neruda #fleabag #phoebe waller bridge #Anna lyndsey #sylvia plath #andrew garfield #tsn #Leah raeder #margaret atwood #death of the friendship #heartbreak #aching #web weaving #parallels #quotes #friend breakup #hannibal

Figure 4. Web weaving titled “Dead friendships: There is a hint of tragedy in the neglected corpse that lays between us, one we can never talk about.”

1.3.2 Web Weaving and Transformational Fanworks

This research positions web weaving as a fan reading practice that is at the nexus of Tumblr’s transformational multifandom culture. On Tumblr, many users follow, post about, and engage with multiple fandoms simultaneously. The dashboard interface exposes users to

a constant stream of content from varied fandoms, and personal blogs often reflect users' engagement with different fictional universes, genres, and media texts through transformative fanworks. Transformative fanworks are distinct aspect of transformational fandom, which is "all about laying hands upon the source and twisting it to the fans' own purposes, whether that is to fix a disappointing issue (a distinct lack of sex-having between two characters, of course, is a favorite issue to fix) in the source material, or using the source material to illustrate a point, or just to have a whale of a good time" (obsession_inc in Fanlore's entry of 'Transformational Fandom', n.d). Through transformative fanworks, fans express their intense attachments to media texts by interpreting the source text based on their desires. By expanding upon, transforming or diverging from the authorial storyworld through creative fanworks and online discourse, fans in digital fan ecosystems like Tumblr challenge the traditional authority identity of texts. Web weaving also emerges as a distinct fan reading practice where fans privilege their intense feelings or 'feels' to interpret various media texts and curate them together.

It is important to consider web weaving as a 'fragmentary' reading practice. The fragmentary nature of web weaving brings together bits and pieces of Tumblr users' affective reception towards their media engagements. By observing how web weaves capture the intensities of sentiment through its fragmentary form, Rose suggests that web weaving is an affective practice: "A thought or experience becomes whole not through a perfect articulation, but through the meshing of related ideas ...[that is] largely incommunicable but deeply felt" (Rose 2023, 10). Web weaving is not just about collating fragments; it is about transforming multiple texts into a fragmentary form through 'intertextuality' (a multivalent literary concept I shall use loosely to refer to meanings of text shaped by other texts), allowing users to dwell, reflect and communicate responses towards texts they deeply feel as readers but cannot fully explain without juxtaposing them alongside other texts. They can be considered what De Kosnik (2016) calls 'acts of remembrance' of the source text and the "affective charge fans experience when interacting with the source text" (46). In this way, we can think of Tumblr users who curate fragments in this practice as archivists of 'feels' towards media texts.

Approaching web weaving as a fan reading practice invites deeper inquiries into how the reading strategies in web weaving are influenced by the transformative digital fan culture of Tumblr. To explore this question, I turn to Rita Felski's modes of textual engagement, namely, 'recognition', 'enchantment, and knowledge', as a framework to closely read the interaction between media texts and the affective reception of Tumblr users in web weaving.

1.3.3 Reading through Web Weaving

In *Uses of Literature* (2008), Felski opens with a manifesto that reflects on the theoretical fatigue that plagues contemporary literary scholarship, as scholars struggle to

articulate the uses of literature beyond critical reading. She suggests that “problematizing, interrogating, and subverting are the default options to do literary theory in the contemporary age (2). So, how can literary scholars continue to make a compelling case for the value of reading in an academic environment where readers must renounce their affective style of engagement with texts in favour of “analytical detachment, critical distance, and guarded suspicion” (2) to be considered as legitimate literary scholars?

Reaffirming Sedgwick (1997) and Ricoeur’s belief that “the hermeneutics of suspicion is now virtually *de rigueur* in literary theory, rather than one option among others”, Felski is deeply sceptical of these dominant fashionable trends that she calls “theological and ideological styles of reading” (3). Theological reading applauds the qualities of literature to a point that they dismiss everyday readers who enjoy reading for knowledge or entertainment as naive for not understanding literature as “literature”—an untouchable, sacred, ineffable force that cannot be fully understood or connected to everyday life. On the other hand, Felski believes ideological reading has cut off the possibility that literature might possess its own kind of knowledge or value beyond what theory extracts from it, resulting in the veneration of the critic rather than the text as the source of knowledge. While in the former, the elite group of experts determine the sacrosanct value of literature to keep it separate from social experiences, the latter diagnoses the values of literature by reducing texts to symptoms of ideological social structures. In the case of ideological reading, she points toward the usual suspects, the roster of Marxist critics and post-structuralist critical French theorists, who have undoubtedly influenced generations of literary academics, but have also contributed to the virality of ‘hermeneutics of suspicion’ in literature classrooms that silence the text beneath critical theory. Both these forms of reading stand in stark contrast to fan reading that tends to resist academic tendencies to sanctify literature as untouchable and elevate the critic as the sole arbiter of meaning. Instead, it aligns more closely with affective and experiential forms of engagement, grounded in the reception of readers, as meaningful ways of interpretation.

Felski’s book (2008) asserts a deceptively simple yet profound claim that the value of literature resides in the reading experience of readers. Her work is determined to retrieve what is lost when literature is subjected to the ‘permanent diagnosis’ of critical reading (2008, 1). It is important to note that she is not critical of literary theory as a field itself. Rather than abandoning theory and turning her back on scholarly interpretation of texts, she instead advocates for a closer theoretical look at readers’ engagement with literature that answers why and how readers are moved by texts.

By calling for a restocking of the literary theory toolbox, Felski proposes “that reading involves a logic of recognition; that aesthetic experience has analogies with enchantment in a supposedly disenchanted age; that literature creates distinctive configurations of social knowledge; [and] that we may value the experience of being shocked by what we read” (14). She conceptualizes recognition, enchantment, knowledge and shock

as modes of textual engagements with text that bring to the forefront the affective dimensions of lay reading as opposed to academic critical reading. She does not suggest one is better than the other, but she pushes back against the assumption that critical readings legitimize the value of literature by arguing that the valorization of this mode of reading in academic circles itself has become uncritical. Felski's modes of textual engagement have direct implications for fan studies. The core of Felski's arguments implicitly acknowledges the readings of fans as an alternative hermeneutic framework. Fans may not always analyze media texts through what literary theorists define as 'critical reading', but their deeply felt responses and creative reinterpretations through fan activities still constitute meaningful forms of interpretation. By studying the textual modes of engagements of fans with media texts, this thesis comprehends how web weaving, as a fan practice, curates and archives 'feels', resulting in possibilities for readerly subjectivities that diverge from those traditionally valorized within academic literary circles.

1.4 Conceptual Focus

In the age of digital hyperconnectivity, the entirety of human experience has been absorbed into a relentless stream of digital content and has reshaped the ways we read media texts, feel about them and record our reception towards them. This research aims to explore this convergence of feeling, reading, and archiving on Tumblr through the practice of web weaving. To exist within the hyper-accessibility of superabundant digital media means consuming content as a nomadic gathering of fragments—jumping from one platform to another, scrolling through an endless flow of content within algorithmic infrastructures engineered to captivate our attention. Yet, the case of web weaving, as a platformed cultural practice, reveals that meaning-making in Tumblr culture is not just about reading through fragments; it is also about threading connections between these disjointed fragments. These connections are guided by readers' experiences of the texts that privilege feeling, otherwise known as 'affective reception'.

The study of web weaving as a fragmentary fan reading practice reveals it as a quintessential expression of Tumblr's transformational fan culture. Tracing the relationship between web weaving and Tumblr's digital fandom culture results in questions about the dynamic feedback loop between Tumblr's platform technological infrastructure and platform vernacular. This has enabled the social blogging platform to become not just a site for the circulation of fan practices, but an archival environment for users to curate and preserve the emotional responses evoked by users' media experiences (often memetically referred to as 'feels'). In this affective atmosphere, often theorised as 'culture of feels', I examine how user blogs function as Snelson's 'little databases' that preserve their passions and interests through 'archontic productions' such as web weaves. My analysis demonstrates that these 'archontic' fan practices have led to Tumblr functioning as what Cvetkovich terms an 'archive of feelings'.

In order to examine users' affective engagements with media texts through web weaving, I employ a 'methodological bricolage' approach of multimodal analysis that centers reading for affect. Ultimately, in the digitally hyperconnected age where we feel, live, and read in fragments, this research closely reads web weaving through Felski's framework to substantiate that the value of literature in a fragmentary reading culture still lies in the deeply felt experiences of reading. Readers often feel seen, transformed, and swept away by media texts. They seek to archive these responses through fan practices such as web weaving. My analysis remains critical of the fact that digital cultural practices are governed by platform capitalism, which pervades the age of digital hyperconnectivity. This is why certain feelings of affective reception become more legible, shareable, and culturally validated due to the platform's design, affordances and cultural vernacular. Web weaving as a fan practice in Tumblr's 'culture of feels' is no exception to this logic.

Chapter 2 Methodologies, Ethics and Research Design

Developing your method as a bricolage means placing your specific research task at the centre of your considerations, and allowing your particular combination and application of methods take shape in relation to the needs that characterise the given task. — Simon Lindgren (2017, 82)

2.1 A ‘Bricolage’ of Methodologies

Having laid the conceptual groundwork to explore web weaving as a fragmentary literary practice, this chapter outlines the methodological approach and research design I adopt to analyze this Tumblr fan practice. Expanding on Rose’s research, I argue that web weaving constitutes a form of literary engagement with media texts that is inseparable from fandom expression on Tumblr. Fandom on Tumblr is sprawling and heterogeneous, with a cacophony of voices clustered around varying fan expressions. Having said that, the communication practices that have emerged through Tumblr’s interface favorably prove that reading on Tumblr becomes a performative expression of personal connection to media through the critical and creative labor of fan practices. In the case of web weaving, reading takes the form of a participatory, curatorial, and multifandom practice that operates through Tumblr’s platform infrastructure and fannish vernacular. As such, my research design recognizes that web weaving cannot be fully interpreted as a cultural text without accounting for Tumblr’s fan culture, user experience, and platform affordances that sustain this creative fan practice.

To engage with the dynamic complexity of this case study, I draw on Lindgren’s (2017) approach to methodology in social media research as a form of ‘bricolage.’ Popularized by Claude Lévi-Strauss (1966), ‘bricolage’ refers to improvising with available materials to create works in new adaptive ways. Lindgren extends this into a methodological approach, describing it as a research strategy that is not entirely predetermined but instead emerges as a patchwork of evolving solutions in response to the problems encountered during research (2017, 282).

I contend that fan studies as a discipline possesses the very spirit of bricolage. Booth and Williams (2021) proclaim that fan studies, as a “discipline, is famously undisciplined” due to its dispersed multidisciplinary nature (12). Researchers who call themselves fan scholars borrow freely from cultural studies, media studies, literary studies, sociology, sports studies, and gender studies, since there are no fixed ‘Fan Studies’ departmental homes. For fan scholars, fan studies “becomes a space where the conventions of [our] originary disciplines can be relaxed; where we can engage in experimentation; where we can admit that we have feelings, that we are passionate about the things we study.” (Vist et al. 2021, 29).

The multidisciplinary porousness of the field makes methodological bricolage a well-suited approach for articulating both the methodological improvisation in fan studies research and the personal commitments of academics-turned-fans and fans-turned-academics. However, like fandom itself, fan studies is not a utopia. The field remains entangled in hierarchies that reproduce exclusion, including racial inequities in scholarship. As Vist and colleagues (2021, 30) remind us, “fandom is messy! How could fan studies be anything but?” Thus, I approach bricolage not only as a flexible method but as a critical and reflexive academic practice grounded in multiplicity, marginal voices, and resistance to disciplinary closure.

In this study, bricolage serves as a methodological strategy that captures the layered, participatory, and affectively charged nature of web weaving on Tumblr. By combining multimodal discourse analysis (Jewitt 2014), platform studies approach (Alberto 2021), and affect theory (Berg et al. 2019), my methodological bricolage is responsive to participatory modes of fannish expression within Tumblr’s multimodal multifandom environment, ultimately to better understand the practice of web weaving.

2.2 Multimodal Discourse Analysis

Tiidenberg et al. (2021) note in their study that Tumblr is a highly multimodal platform. Firstly, the term 'multimodal' itself warrants clarification. Carey Jewitt (2014), synthesizing Gunther Kress’s seminal scholarship on multimodality, defines it as an approach that “understand[s] communication and representation to be more than about language and which attend[s] to the full range of communicational forms people use—image, gesture, gaze, posture, and so on—and the relationships between them” (14). The core idea behind multimodality is that meaning is produced, circulated, interpreted, consumed, contextualized, and recontextualized through many representational and communicative modes that move beyond the textual modes of language. Simply put, modes are semiotic resources in cultures for meaning-making. On Tumblr, this includes a variety of media types: long- and short-form text, still images, GIFs, hyperlinks, video, audio, quotations, and chat posts (Figure 5). Each constitutes a semiotic mode that contributes to a larger multimodal ensemble when users compose a post.

Figure 5. Tumblr’s multimodal post options.

Jewitt outlines four principles of multimodal theory that shape my multimodal methodological approach to Tumblr:

- Language is part of a multimodal ensemble.
- Each mode in a multimodal ensemble realizes different communicative work.
- People orchestrate meaning through their selection and configuration of modes.
- The meanings of signs are shaped by the norms and rules operating at the moment of sign-making, influenced by the motivations and interests of the sign-maker in a specific social context. (Jewitt 2014, 14-16)

Tumblr blogs, then, can be understood as multimodal ensembles. Jewitt and Kress (2014), in their study of food blogs, describe blogs as “archived posts comprised of multimedia, or what we shall call here multimodal, digitally produced materials displayed on screens that are chronologically sequenced by the blog platform and thematically organized by the blogger” (2). Acknowledging blogs as archives of multimodal posts, my study situates Tumblr blogs within the ontology of the digital archive. I analyze the multimodality of Tumblr blogs as personalized, user-curated archives since blogs are saturated with a variety of semiotic resources that are curated and then reblogged by users for other users. Meaning on Tumblr arises not only from the content of a post but from the relationality between posts, reblogs, and the user’s curatorial impulse. This affirms Jewitt’s claim that users as sign-makers select and circulate meaning in relation to their own passions and priorities that determine which posts are produced, selected, tagged, and reblogged.

Since Tumblr is a participatory communal platform, no matter what type of post a user creates, the act of reblogging yields the possibility of transforming the post into a collaborative multimodal text. By reblogging, every user adds their own perspective to a Tumblr post through various semiotic modes; thus, each Tumblr post oscillates between contextualization and recontextualization due to reblogs. The role of a reblog is distinct from other platform features, say, ‘tags.’ Tags are used for both categorization and commentary of a user’s intimate expression. Therefore, platform features such as reblogging, tagging, commenting, and multimedia post options offer specific possibilities or affordances for different kinds of communicative work. But affordances are always perceived by the actions of users. Following Jewitt’s argument, I also consider how users on Tumblr have developed community norms or platform vernacular that govern the nature of these affordances. For example, tagging on Tumblr is not just metadata or an affordance of discoverability; it has become a conversational space. In this way, my analysis of Tumblr will center on the modes of platform affordances (what Tumblr enables or constrains) and vernaculars (how users have developed communal norms of their usage) for various meaning-making practices in the multimodal environment of Tumblr.

A platform studies perspective in fan studies helps me further frame this analysis. I use the term platforms here to refer broadly to digital spaces that organize user content and interaction. Maria Alberto’s platform-studies approach (2021) influences my reading of

Tumblr not as a set of technical infrastructures alone, but as a space where the relationship between the platform affordances and users communities have given rise to various fan practices on these platforms (Alberto 2021, 234). In this sense, I will look at sociotechnical infrastructure, platform affordances and platform vernacular as modes/semiotic resources that cultivate the discursive practices of production, circulation, curation, and consumption of fan content on Tumblr.

Web weaving is a discursive practice that is the focal point of my research. Through multimodal discourse analysis, I examine the orchestration of various fragmentary semiotic resources—text, poetry, film stills, screenshots, and images—into sequential collage-like web weaving, as well as the tags, captions, and reblog chains that accompany them. I read web weaving as a multimodal text that relies on the affective reception of readers in Tumblr’s multifandom culture with its multimodal affordances and platform vernaculars. By focusing on how Tumblr users configure and reconfigure meaning across media texts, I show how Tumblr users have created a multimodal cultural text of web weaving.

2.3 Affect as a Multimodal Practice

The complexity of multimodal discourse analysis presents a challenge of systematically analyzing diverse modes, due to their differing semiotic nature and function. To address this, I found Westberg’s (2021) article “Affect as a Multimodal Practice” particularly insightful for grounding multimodality in empirical research by studying affect in discourse. His work contributes to the burgeoning field of affective discursive studies, which treats affect and emotion as the outcomes of meaning-making practices. This perspective urges us to examine how emotions are discursively mobilized to perform ideological, political, and social functions. Westberg’s framework to approach affect through the lens of multimodality is underpinned by the conviction that meaning-making through affect is not restricted to a specific semiotic mode and is applicable to potentially all modes.

According to Westberg, affect and emotion are not antithetical. Rather, affect is conceived as a “relational concept that signifies intersubjective experiences and their performative role in the formation of collective subjectivities, identities, and belongings through discourse... [where] emotions are conceived of as being accomplished, circulated, and semiotically materialized in affective-discursive practice” (Westberg 2021, 24). His analysis demonstrates that studying emotion in affective-discursive practices requires close examination of how affect is built and activated by multimodal materials situated within particular socio-political discourses. Drawing upon Ahmed’s ‘stickiness’ of emotions (2004), Westberg emphasizes the performative role of emotions that position people into particular subjectivities (“the patriotic citizen” or “the proud consumer”) and groups them into communities within discourses. Westberg illustrates this with a case study on indigenous capitalism by examining Sámi people’s cultural representations through the semiotics of

clothing, food, and images in tourism advertising. He analyzes these semiotic modes that are framed to evoke ‘happiness’ in the advertising discourse. Here, affect is not seen as something inherent in the semiotic materials themselves, but it emerges in the interaction between the affordances of these modes and the lived experience and social positioning of audiences who view these advertisements. Studying this interaction provides an empirical approach to tracing how affective meanings are produced, circulated, and felt through the multimodal performance of emotions in discourse.

The outlook of affect as relational, emergent, and materialized in multimodal discourse finds further methodological development in Berg et al.’s (2019) methodological proposal for analyzing affective dynamics in discourse. While Westberg shows how affect circulates through semiotic modes, Berg and colleagues address the methodological challenge of reading such affective dynamics in discourse. Their methodological proposal offers a close reading method grounded in similar convictions that affect must not be studied only as a pre-discursive intensity but as a discursive process. They critique the binary between affect and discourse found in the Deleuzian school of affect advanced by Brian Massumi (2002), which conceptualizes affect as something bodily, immediate, and inassimilable by language. Berg and colleagues convince the readers that locating affect entirely outside language makes it difficult to read affect empirically or theoretically. Feminist scholars like Berlant (1997, 2011), Cvetkovich (2003, 2012), and Ahmed (2004) have been critical of the bifurcation of affect and discursive meaning. They attempt to resolve this tension by asking how affect is materialized in discourse as emotion and by whom? They do not divorce affect from emotion. Judith Butler also provides a productive middle ground by suggesting that while the subject emerges belatedly in discourse, this emergence is always affectively charged. As she writes, “I am already affected before I can say ‘I,’ and I have to be affected to say ‘I’ at all” (Berg et al. 2019, 48). Affect, then, is not outside language but circulates within it, affecting and being affected by discourse.

My project is guided by this idea of affect as something that does not reside in bodies but as an ongoing relational process between discourse bodies. The relational interactions between bodies in discourse through material forms (spoken, written, visual, gestural) evoke affective responses. Importantly, Berg et al. (2019) caution against reading these responses as discrete emotions like anger, fear, or shame only in the realm of subjective feelings. Instead, they take inspiration from Ahmed (2004) to propose that we study how such emotion-words function as affective intensities in discourse, such as how they move between bodies, shape relationships, and become associated with certain social groups or positions. This is what their method, ‘Reading for Affect,’ attempts to realize. ‘Reading for Affect’ foregrounds affect as a hermeneutic lens to understand discourse. It involves “tracing emotion words and their genealogies, metaphors, and analogies involving bodies or a bodily becoming, vocabulary indicating subjective feelings and experiences, and the materiality of discourse

itself to lay open how the affective relations between different bodies are established through language” (Berg et al. 2019, 52). In other words, ‘reading for affect’ studies cultural meanings of emotions, tracking the use of embodied metaphors, analogies, or emotion-words in language to understand how discourse bodies affect or are affected in social systems.

In my opinion, this methodological approach fits well with Lamerich’s theoretical framework of ‘affective reception.’ According to Lamerichs, emotions are conscious and productive outcomes of fans’ engagement with media texts, often clearly expressed through fan practices in online media fandom discourses. By applying the method of reading for affect, I trace how fans read with ‘feels’ within Tumblr fan discourse through the practice of web weaving. My study involves close reading of emotion-related vocabulary, bodily metaphors, and accompanying expressive Tumblr reblogs, tags, and captions in web weaving, which work together as a multimodal ensemble to construct affective relationships between fans and disparate media texts. Here, Rita Felski’s (2008) textual modes of engagement, recognition, enchantment, and knowledge are particularly relevant. These textual modes of engagement offer a vocabulary to describe what kind of affective dynamics are present during the fragmentary fan reading practice of web weaving. Thus, Felski’s theory complements the method of ‘Reading for Affect’ by theorizing how fans form relational affective dynamics between disparate media texts in web weaving and what role Tumblr as a platform plays in these affective dynamics. In this manner, this cultural studies research also opens new ground for close reading in a neoliberal environment that heavily promotes big data techniques to study platformed fan culture in attention economies of digital hyperconnectivity.

2.4 Data Collection, Ethics and Positionality

This study adopts a hashtag-based social media research method to collect Tumblr posts as objects of analysis. The dataset comprises two primary categories: (1) web weaving posts and (2) meta-Tumblr posts.

1. **Web Weaving Posts:** The #webweaving hashtag marked the rise of web weaving as a recognizable practice on Tumblr. Related tags such as #parallels, #comparatives, and #poetry also serve to curate and categorize web weaving posts. Using these hashtags, I identified and collected approximately 50 original web weaving posts dated between 2019 and 2024. Rather than pursuing a representative sample, I used this broad survey to trace thematic, aesthetic, and formal patterns in the posts. The selected examples allow for close multimodal readings of their visual, textual, and intertextual qualities, including the affective responses visible in user-added tags and reblogs. All posts were screenshotted, indexed, anonymized, and archived in a private Tumblr blog created specifically for this research (Figure 6: <https://archiveoffeels.tumblr.com/>), which remains private to protect user anonymity and minimize ethical risks in citing user-generated research.

2. **Meta-Tumblr Posts:** My research also endeavors to demonstrate the function of Tumblr blogs as a personal archive curated by users for their perusal. I collected around 30 posts from what Tiidenberg et al. (2020) term the “meta-fandom of Tumblr”—posts where users reflect on Tumblr’s affordances, cultural sensibilities, and communication norms, particularly as they relate to fan culture and blogging as a curatorial practice. Users share a passionate love-hate relationship with Tumblr. This passion has rendered Tumblr an object of fannish attention. Many users are fans of the Tumblr fan culture in itself, often “commemorat[ing] inside jokes about the platform’s various features and functions” (Tiddenberg et al. 2021, 137). I analyze these meta-Tumblr posts to understand the perception of Tumblr users of the platform affordances and vernacular. The private research blog documents these posts as well.

archivists of 'feels'

[@archiveoffeels](#) / [archiveoffeels.tumblr.com](#)

a masters' thesis project on web weaving

Figure 6. Research blog for data collection.

My data collection follows the ethical frameworks established by fan studies scholars such as Kristina Busse (2017), McCracken et al. (2020), and Rose (2025), who caution against positioning online fan spaces as unproblematically public. Busse underscores the importance of preserving the pseudonymous nature of fans’ identities, noting that platforms like Tumblr create a semi-public space where users expect a degree of privacy due to the pseudonymous architecture. She advises scholars to cite fanworks but protect users’ identifying details. Similarly, Crystal Abidin reminds researchers that “just because something is publicly accessible [on platforms like Tumblr] does not mean it is public property” (McCracken et al. 2020, 12). All Tumblr content cited in this thesis has been anonymized—usernames, blog titles, and profile pictures have been redacted. The only exception is the publicly acknowledged contribution of Tumblr user @oumaimas, credited for coining the term web weaving. While this anonymization ethics necessarily removes credit for users’ fan creativity, I align with Rose’s (2025) belief that “this is preferable to infringing on their privacy or safety” (32). I wholeheartedly sympathize with this drawback, and my

research shares this ethical tension. This ethical choice is also particularly necessary due to the complexity of authorship in reblog chains and the personal nature of testimonial tags, which makes obtaining informed consent nearly impossible.

An equally crucial ethical principle in fan studies is recognizing the researcher's positionality and personal bias. As noted earlier, fan studies occupy an infamously undisciplined disciplinary space where scholars are both academics-turned-fans and fans-turned-academics. Since scholars often bring their fannish selves into their academic work, either consciously or unconsciously, Busse (2017) piercingly spells out the need to remain vigilant about the ways this influences their selection of texts and interpretive frameworks. Scholars may gravitate toward the creative, uplifting aspects of fandom while sidelining messier or more contentious issues. Transparency about positionality, then, becomes essential.

In my case, I approach this project as a queer fan scholar of colour. I have first been a reader and then a fan and only later a researcher (strictly in that order). I was drawn to Tumblr's sprawling queer and feminist fan cultures as a teenager. Tumblr has long served as a formative space for my fannish reading, writing, and interpretive activities, particularly around queer readings, transformative fan practices, and centering marginalized voices of people of colour in white-dominated, Western-centric Tumblr fandoms. Today, Tumblr has become a site for my scholarly activity. My investment in the topic arises from the desire to record reading traditions of fragmentation in digital cultures, particularly in a subcultural platform like Tumblr that mainstream discourse has prematurely declared "dead" since 2018 (Minkel 2023). Although my personal experiences inform my interest in Tumblr's literary and fan cultures, any observation, description, and theory mentioned in this study carries the imprint of broader scholarly discourse on fan cultures, Tumblr, digital platform cultures, and digital reading practices. My project advocates for the recognition of Tumblr as a meaningful cultural site of 'feels' with understudied fan practices like web weaving. But this advocacy does not come at the expense of casting Tumblr as a utopian fan space. The critical lens of this project lies in holding space for both appreciation and critical reflection. I analyze the platformed social forces that condition modes of fan participation and privilege certain affective dynamics of fans with media texts more than others. My goal is not to reduce Tumblr's dynamic fan spaces to detached scientific objectivity through the 'hermeneutics of suspicion' form of academic reading. Instead, I choose to interpret the messiness of Tumblr's fan culture activities as meaningful reading practices influenced by the fragmentation of contemporary reading habits and the growing platformization of fan culture.

2.5 Research Questions

This thesis introduces web weaving as a compelling case study to explore the fragmentary nature of fan reading practices emerging from Tumblr's platformized fan culture.

Having established the conceptual and methodological frameworks that inform this study, I now return to the core question proposed at the outset: What does it mean to be a reader in a hyperconnected yet fragmented digital world characterised by the platformization of fan culture?

In the chapters that follow, I examine how fans interpret, perform, archive, and circulate their reading experiences through the fan reading practice of web weaving. While web weaving at first glance appears novel due to its fragmentary, curatorial, and affective mode of fan reception, my analysis argues that web weaving is an expression of Tumblr's underlying disposition as a digital user-driven archive of feelings. In doing so, I address the subsequent questions in my analysis:

- (1) How do the platform affordances and communication norms of Tumblr, as a mediated platform for transformative fan culture, affect the mode of expression in web weaving?
- (2) In what ways does web weaving as a fragmentary fan reading practice illustrate how Tumblr users read, interpret, and engage with media texts?

In the first half of my study (Chapter 3), I focus on the platform architecture (reblogging, tagging, engagement metrics called notes, pseudonymity, algorithms, and multimodal post options), affordances (interactivity, non-linear temporality, and scalability, pseudonymity, and searchability), and vernacular (social curation, personal testimonial and multimodal multiliterate multifandom literacies). Together, they constitute an archival environment for Tumblr's affective fandom economies that are neither outside platformization nor wholly subsumed by rapacious extractive platform capitalism, where user blogs function as "little databases" of fannish interests. The archival and affective environment of Tumblr's transformative fan culture underscores the archontic nature of fan practices, which is also central to web weaving.

The second part of my analysis (Chapter 4) examines the case study of web weaving as a fragmentary fan reading practice in detail. I situate this relatively novel fan practice within the lineage of fragmentary fan practices on Tumblr (moodboards, gifsets, and text post memes). This historical context highlights that web weaving is not a sole fragmentary fan reading practice that exists on Tumblr; but it is the one that undeniably makes visible the fragmentation and platformization of reading practices. The close reading of web weaving posts, along with users' perspectives on web weaving, dives deeper into the affective dynamics of users and media texts through Felski's modes of textual engagement. The affective reception of users in these Tumblr posts substantiates that web weaving reflects and responds to the archival and transformative impulse of Tumblr's platformed 'culture of feels.' However, it also reveals how fragmentation and platformization shape which media texts and

affective responses gain visibility within Tumblr's affective fandom economies. This analysis remains sensitive to how such affective responses often reproduce dominant, racialized subjectivities, generating tensions within web weaving communities. As the form circulates more widely, it increasingly heroes a narrow repertoire of media texts and modes of feeling, relying on the repeated use of familiar quotes and artworks in ways that strip them of context, often to the detriment of the marginalized voices from which they originate. These patterns of decontextualization, canonization, and rising monetization in the practice reflect broader real-world biases that come into play in the circulatory affect of this practice. In participating in the endless reproduction and 'value-added' logic of platform capitalism, where affective engagement has become a source for monetization. Contrary to claims in earlier scholarship, web weaving can no longer be uncritically read as a counter-hegemonic or anti-capitalist practice.

Chapter 3 Tumblr as Platformed Archive of Feelings

Tumblr seemed like a terrain of affinities speaking at a thousand miles a minute, one that regarded written language as a simple, runty cousin. My feeling of disorientation upon first entering the space was like being immersed in language that didn't quite make sense—all there was was the gist. I sensed that there was something else being circulated here, something that resisted definition and classic semiotic formulas. It seemed, from the first moments I was in the space, that Tumblr traded in affect. — Alexander Cho (2015, 44)

3.1 Short History of Tumblr

Tumblr introduces itself today with the tagline: *Fandom, Art, Chaos*. But what, precisely, makes it a hub for all three? For context, let's take a brief detour through its history, which has sustained fan communities as a core part of its user base for nearly two decades.

Founded in 2007 by then 21-year-old David Karp, Tumblr was envisioned as a highly customizable, user-driven publishing platform targeted at 'creators.' Originating during the formative years of Web 2.0, Karp resisted Silicon Valley's metrics-obsessed culture in the platforms of Google+, Facebook, and Twitter. He infamously found user categorization through follower counts "really gross," believing the culture of public friend-following "can... really poison a whole community" (Walker 2012). Inspired by early microblogging experiments like Projectionist and Anarchia, Karp envisioned Tumblr as a multimedia creative space, where users can post and share long- and short-form text, images, audio, GIFs, video, and links and offering.

This ethos of multimedia flexibility made Tumblr stand out, especially when compared to platforms like Facebook, Blogger, Twitter, and LiveJournal (McCracken et al. 2020, 4). At the same time, it was notoriously non-intuitive (and would continue to remain so) due to its complex interface, faulty navigation, and searchability features. But its pseudonymous usernames (in contrast to Facebook's real-name policy), unique interaction mechanisms, and idiosyncratic algorithmic design created a barrier for uninvested outsiders, giving invested users creative autonomy and control. Stein (2017, 87) also notes that this "illegibility to outsiders" was part of Tumblr's appeal, especially for fandoms migrating from LiveJournal after the social networking and journaling platform banned erotic fanfiction. After the exodus of LiveJournal users, "fanfiction migrated to Archive of Our Own, but a void was left in terms of the more visual and social aspects of the culture, which Tumblr rose to fill" (Tiidenberg et al. 2021, 116). The design of the blog as a public-private space also

made Tumblr conducive to fan engagement (see section 3.5). As a result, though not originally built for fans, fandom quickly became central to Tumblr’s identity.

The ownership of Tumblr was a tumultuous affair that ironically cemented the platform’s subcultural identity. In the early 2010s, Tumblr’s mainstream rise was steep but stable. As a New York-based startup outside Silicon Valley with a progressive company culture and user-aligned ethos, Tumblr supported adult content and resisted aggressive ad-revenue models (McCracken et al. 2020, 7). These two distinct features would put Tumblr in between a rock and a hard place in later years. Ads did exist but remained largely unobtrusive and non-personalized due to pseudonymity and a lack of invasive data collection. This cultivated loyal niche communities but also made profitability elusive. Thus began the chaos of corporate handoffs. In 2013, Karp sold Tumblr to Yahoo for \$1.1 billion, which promised not to “screw up” the platform. Although celebrities like Lady Gaga, Taylor Swift, and Barack Obama brought mainstream visibility in its ‘peak’ years, Tumblr’s real strength always remained in its fiercely loyal userbase. But Tumblr’s nonconformist culture clashed with Yahoo’s growth ambitions, and it also lagged during the mobile-first boom. Verizon took over the floundering platform in 2017 and, in 2018, banned adult content to appease advertisers for a sustainable monetization model. This was known as the “Great Porn Ban” in Tumblr’s lore, which disproportionately disenfranchised queer and trans communities, and nearly 30% of users left (McCracken et al. 2020; Tiidenberg et al. 2021). Eventually, post-2018, Tumblr “died” in the popular imagination (Minkel 2023). In 2019, it was quietly sold to Automattic (parent company of WordPress) for under 0.3% of Yahoo’s purchase price. While Automattic now keeps introducing new features and monetization tools, most are still poorly received by users.

Tumblr’s inability to be easily monetized became part of its culture. “Tumblr is always dying” (Figure 7) became an inside joke among users. In the wake of rising platform capitalism, since Tumblr was too unruly to easily profit from, it became too beloved for users to abandon (McCracken et al. 2020, 9). As Amanda Brennan, Tumblr’s former Head of Content Insights, put it, the platform’s “blessing for it as a user is a curse for it as a business” (Hoover 2025). Yet this dysfunction enabled Tumblr to remain resilient in a post-pandemic world increasingly defined by optimization, commodification, and surveillance. Recent waves of Gen Z migration suggest Tumblr’s life is far from over (Hoover 2025). After Musk’s acquisition of Twitter (now X) intensified algorithmic policing, many sought refuge on Tumblr in 2023. That same year, Reddit’s controversial API pricing led to another influx. In 2025, the near-banning of TikTok in the U.S. triggered a spike in sign-ups once again.

This panic happens like every few months.

Figure 7. Meme showing Tumblr's ironic humor about Tumblr's decline.⁴

Despite these bursts of periodic attention, Tumblr remains a sequestered cultural space. For users, Tumblr's subcultural identity has never relied on virality but on circulation within niche audiences defined by shared aesthetics and creative norms. While fandom remains central, Tumblr also houses subcultures around queerness, mental health, social justice, art, and writing. But ultimately, it is important to note that it is still a for-profit platform, not immune to governance, monetization, and platform capitalism. Scholars believe Tumblr's 'hands-off' legacy has left more space for counter-hegemonic content than platforms like Instagram, where such posts are often shadowbanned⁵ (Frieder 2025, 22, Cho 2022). It remains a popular opinion that in the climate of algorithmic surveillance and influencer capitalism, Tumblr blogs for loyal users continue to remain their "flow of consciousness" and a "diary" (Hoover 2025). This brings me to the central provocation of this chapter: What is it about Tumblr's design, affordances, and culture that makes it feel like a flow of consciousness, a diary, or, as I claim, an archive of feelings? To what extent can Tumblr still be considered a counter-hegemonic space when the platform still seeks to monetize affective engagement, and the freedom of self-expression as the performance of 'feels' within its affective fandom economies is not equally distributed?

3.2 Platform Structure

Tumblr is accessible via both browser and app. As of 2025, its design can be broadly understood through four core components:

a. **Blog Interface:** A user's blog is their public-facing webpage, formatted as `username.tumblr.com` (Figure 6: `archiveoffeels.tumblr.com`). It hosts both original posts and

⁴ A still from *It's Always Sunny in Philadelphia* (2005) originally captioned, "Everybody's dying, bitch. Let's get you some fruit"

⁵ Shadowbanning is a practice where social media platforms subtly restrict a user's content visibility without explicitly informing them

reblogs of other users’ content, with significant customization made possible through built-in themes or user-modified HTML, CSS, and JavaScript.

b. **Dashboard Interface:** The user’s “dash,” or dashboard, serves as Tumblr’s central content feed (Figure 8). Initially designed as a reverse chronological stream, it enabled users to reblog and engage with posts through likes, shares, and follows (borrowing some features from broader social media platforms). However, unlike most platforms, follower/following counts are not public by default unless users choose to disclose them, but most keep them hidden. As tech entrepreneur and Karp’s friend Muscarella once put it, “It’s all business in the front... and then the real party is in the back, through the social interaction on the dashboard” (Walker 2012). In 2023, Automattic introduced an algorithmic “For You” tab alongside the classic chronological feed. Crucially, it allows users to toggle or disable the algorithmic feed, an unusual move in an era of algorithmic platforms. Most users rejected it in favour of the chronological dash. As Rose notes, many opted out, and the update was met with widespread disdain (2025, 39). Unlike Instagram or TikTok, Tumblr’s feed for the majority of users remains a largely chronological or near-chronological feed (feed based on your followed tags).

Figure 8. Tumblr Dashboard: Following, For You, and Your Tags pages

c. **Explore Page:** Rolled out in 2011, the Explore Page (Figure 9) curates trending posts and tags based on a metric called ‘notes.’ Unlike platforms like Instagram, YouTube, or X, which separate engagement into likes, shares, and comments, Tumblr combines all forms of interaction—likes, reblogs, tags, and replies—into a single number called ‘notes.’ This accumulative, opaque metric resists ranking different types of engagement and flattens them into one value, making it harder to assign hierarchical or commercial worth to specific actions. On the Explore page, users can also search posts by tag, keyword, or username, and browse trending tags (determined by post popularity, tag frequency and community activity).

However, as we will see, Tumblr’s notoriously chaotic tagging practices and anti-clout culture make searchability uneven at best.

Figure 9. Trending tags and posts on Tumblr’s Explore (as of 21 July 2025)

d. **Communities:** Introduced in late 2024, Tumblr Communities are topic-based spaces with dedicated dashboards, similar to Facebook groups, subreddits, or LiveJournal communities. These can be public or private, moderated by admins, and organized around specific interests. However, uptake has been minimal. In typical Tumblr fashion, many users responded with scepticism, fearing the feature might undermine Tumblr’s core reblogging culture (Figures 10.1 & 10.2). As this feature is still new and peripheral, it falls outside the scope of this project.

#plus i feel like it might further discourage posting/reblogging #undescribed

oh god i didnt even think about that. that's totally what's gonna happen 😞

i love tumblr users immediate distrust of any and all new tumblr features. it's just an inherent part of the culture here

tumblr communities are what discord servers are to forums. i don't want to have to join a community to see fan works or discussions, why are we sectioning things off when you can use the public tags

Figures 10.1-10.2. Poll with 712 votes, illustrating skepticism towards Communities

The critical overview paints a picture of Tumblr’s structure to further comprehend its features and affordances for users who inhabit this interface. I also assess certain platform vernacular, shared conventions and genres of communication practices that have emerged from the affordances of Tumblr and how users interact with them. By examining the dynamic loop of platform affordances and user practices, we begin to see what kinds of emotions circulate within Tumblr’s affective economies and how they come to be shared, archived, curated, and felt across fan communities.

3.3 Platform Features, Affordances, Vernaculars and Counterpublics

In media studies of platformized digital fan culture, the lens of platform affordances is often used to explain the kinds of fan practices users engage in to express themselves online. Affordances refer to the perceived capabilities and constraints of a platform that enable or limit certain forms of self-expression. This focus on perception is crucial, as affordances shape how users imagine and navigate a platform’s expressive potential (Tiidenberg et al. 2021, Oz et al. 2023). While features are the tools built into a platform, affordances reflect how those tools are used, adapted, or resisted by users. Much has been theorized about Tumblr’s affordances (Tiidenberg et al. 2021; McCracken et al. 2021; Cho 2015; Stein 2015, 2017), but because affordances hinge on user perception, my contribution focuses on Tumblr posts where users discuss the platform’s functions. These meta-commentaries, often expressed through ironic, self-aware brand of Tumblr humour, shed light on the vernacular norms deeply attuned to Tumblr’s infrastructural logic. I examine how Tumblr’s evolution as a fandom space resonates with its perceived affordances and shared vernaculars, ultimately fostering the culture of ‘feels.’

3.3.1 Reblogging and ‘Yes-and’ Culture of Multiplicity

Tumblr’s reblog feature cultivates a culture of multiplicity. Reblogging enables users to reproduce and respond to Tumblr posts by adding commentary, tags, and multimodal content, creating a collective multimodal text. Posts can cascade in various directions, spurred by a single catalyst. For example, in the “World War Tea” post (Figure 11), a McDonald’s ad quickly morphed into a humorous yet biting commentary on colonialism and cultural differences, as users shared their perspectives through reblogs, thus quickly shifting the tone and content of the post. Reblogging accretes layers of content and references, oscillates between contexts, loses its original meaning, and gains new context very quickly.

Tiidenberg et al. (2021) theorize the affordances of reblogging as interactivity, non-linear temporality, and scalability. Do Tumblr users feel the same? Interactivity refers to users engaging with one another’s ideas by actively reblogging each other’s content (Tiidenberg et al. 2021, 56). For users, reblogging is the primary mode of interaction. Amidst the 2023–2025 migrations from platforms like Twitter, Reddit, and TikTok, many algorithmically attuned newcomers arrived on Tumblr with expectations shaped by original-content-centric and engagement-optimized interfaces that involved liking, commenting, and passive scrolling. In response, veteran Tumblr users created instructional posts to clarify how the reblog culture values collective meaning-making over metrics or authorship. As seen in Figure 12, the user shares how reblogs are tools of self-expression, signaling emotional investment, fandom affiliation, and discursive participation. Therefore, the act of reblogging supports a polyphonous environment of multiple perspectives and shared interests.

Figure 11. 'World War Tea' post with divergent viewpoints in reblog chains.

When you reblog something, it's like saying...

- You're so excited about the post that you want others to see it
- You agree with the idea/opinion being expressed in the post (opinions, discourse, analysis, etc.)
- You care about the things said in the post (like sharing pro-Palestine posts)
- You identify with the community being represented in the post (like being part of a certain fandom)
- You find the post funny and want to save it (like how you'd save memes to your phone)
- You think the post is cute and want to squish it (cat photos, animal videos, kawaii stuff, etc.)

Figure 12. Excerpt from a Tumblr instructional post on reblog culture for new users.

Reblog's culture of multiplicity speaks to the multiplicity of transformative fandoms. Tumblr's recirculation and reworking of cultural meanings through reblogs resonates with "fandom's valuing of transformative reworking and repeating of tropes and beloved images ... [that emphasize] a multiplicity of interpretations and affective returns to beloved media objects" (Stein 2017, 87). A single post can circulate in countless mutated forms depending on which reblog trail is encountered by a user, resulting in a palimpsest of meanings that resists fixed authorship or singular interpretation. The quintessence of reblog embodies transformational fandom's long-standing modes of intertextual engagement, collaborative authorship, and remix-driven culture. On that account, reblogging constrains linear narratives by making room for a non-linear temporality. Posts are constantly recirculated, reinterpreted, and revived, stimulating an atmosphere of "ephemerality and timelessness" simultaneously (Popova 2017). Cho (2015) theorizes this atmosphere as affective because of reverberation, where repetition of posts through reblogging blurs boundaries between self and collective, forming a shared marginal relational stance that resists dominant cultural norms (2015, 46). Tumblr users express this logic in simpler, humorous terms. Figures 13 and 14 show how users blend humour and critique to rebel against the normative expectations of authorship on social media platforms. On Tumblr, old posts resurface frequently, unlike Instagram, where outdated content is stigmatised or Twitter, where original content is prized. The reblog design constitutes an ever-shifting collective emotional authorship that prioritizes community engagement over individual recognition, where content scales widely across audiences. This scalability has made Tumblr a kind of "yes-and" improv space where each user chimes in by adding to what the previous user posted, as seen in the World War Tea post. We can also see this 'Yes-and' culture in certain web weaving posts that build upon each other, which I will discuss in Chapter 4. The disruption of venerated singular authorship across these

participatory iterative reblog chains strikes at the heart of transformational fan communities that value multiplicity of interpretations over authorial meanings.

It's still so strange to me how apparently taboo it is to like a post on someone's Instagram from a month ago when there are posts still circulating on Tumblr from 1550 BCE

Figure 13. Ironic Tumblr textpost about the cyclical nature of reblogging.

Also, this isn't Twitter. I know that on Twitter, it's largely expected for most of your profile to consist of mostly your own tweets, and not too many retweets. Tumblr is extremely different, in that the entire site is made up of shared posts. The site is designed for maybe 5% of the content on your dash to be original content at any given moment, while 95% will be reblogs from others, and that's perfectly acceptable and expected, actually.

Figure 14. Excerpt from an instructional post on Tumblr's curatorial reblog culture.

Reblogging has evolved into a distinct vernacular of curation on Tumblr. Through reblogs, users often reimagine and reinterpret content to reframe it. Cho (2015) argues “the authorial locus on Tumblr is not the act of creation; it is the act of curation ... [that] relies much more on aesthetics, intimation, sensibility, and movement—in short, affect” (46). Tumblr is not a curatorial platform like Pinterest or Instagram. Pinterest and Instagram are designed as curatorial platforms, where the interface, affordances, and algorithm actively guide users toward creating cohesive, aestheticized, and often aspirational content collections. Tumblr’s curatorial communication practice emerges through social curation, where users imbue posts with new layers of meaning, extending their circulation through reblogs. As a user says, “Tumblr is less focused on the individual voice...it’s not what you’re selling. you can present yourself as a collection of quotes and pictures and ideas” (Frieder 2021, 5). Unlike media environments shaped by algorithmically segmented, feed-based individualism, identity performance on Tumblr does not emphasize cohesive self-branding; rather, it circulates affect through social curation. By embracing the nonlinear rhythms of reblog culture, the user (Figure 15) shares that Tumblr is meant to be consumed as a patchwork of messy, polyphonous fragments, curated not through coherence, but through personal interests and desires. Though a public platform, Tumblr users perceive it as a private space: a place where users perform self-expression while also curating feelings, atmospheres, and fragments that speak to their inner worlds in a networked platform.

my dash is like "shitpost" "important sociopolitical event" "fandom fuckery" "queer discourse" "vague hornyposting" "advice for adulthood" "calls for a boycott of companies for xyz reasons" "series of gifs of a show i don't watch" "cute cat" and i think that's how this hellsite was meant to be consumed

Figure 15. Social curation on Tumblr via reblogs.

In sum, Tumblr’s reblog feature encapsulates key aspects of digital fandom today: a culture of multiplicity, non-linear temporality, collective emotional authorship, the “yes-and” principle, and vernacular practices of curatorial self-expression. Through reblogs, Tumblr enables users to create and inhabit a fragmentary reading culture grounded in feeling, transformation, and participation.

3.3.2 Tagging Intimacies and Curated Folksonomies

The imaginary of Tumblr as a public-private space is most evident in its tagging practices. Tags across platforms like Instagram and Twitter function as classification tools for searchability and algorithmic visibility. By granting tags full sentences, punctuation, and spaces, Tumblr invites a different kind of use. Here, tags become a space for both personal curation and commentary, enabling what McCracken et al. call “performative signalling within collective Tumblr networks” (6). Tumblr tags are broadly used in two ways: (1) subjective categorization, where users organize posts through personal taxonomies (e.g., #this made me cry, #poetry, #things i like, see Figure 16 for more subjective tagging), and (2) expressive commentary, where tags function as discursive or affective extensions of the post.

Figure 16. Tumblr user’s tag directory illustrating curated folksonomies,

The first use of tags affords a ‘curated folksonomy’ for users. This term by Bulliard (2019) can be used to describe the practice of tagging on Tumblr because “curated

folksonomies are primarily reactive; unlike traditional, top-down controlled vocabulary approaches, most of the terms in a curated folksonomy are driven by user activity, and intentional knowledge organization design follows user action” (10). Curated folksonomies then allow for a prioritization of subjectivity in tag classifications as users apply their own aesthetic, emotional, and political taxonomies to curate their blogs. Still, some standardization occurs. Fandom-specific tags like #bts, #taylor swift, or ship names⁶ like #stucky⁷ and #firstprince⁸ gain traction because large, active fan communities rely on shared tags to maintain visibility in fan communities. Other tags catch on more organically. The tag #webweaving, for instance, became popular after user @oumaimas used it to describe a specific intertextual collage form. Even with these patterns, tagging on Tumblr remains largely expressive and idiosyncratic, unlike the structured discoverability on algorithm-driven platforms. Tumblr’s flawed search tool frustrates users and contributes to its reputation as a ‘hellsite,’ but many loyal users embrace this imperfection. As shown in Figures 17.1-17.2, users often see the dashboard’s ephemerality, where posts reappear through reblogs and tags rather than search, as part of the platform’s charm. This ephemerality, in turn, prompts them to develop their own curated tagging system as a form of subjective archiving.

i think a lot of the magic of this shithole website actually comes from the fact that the search feature is completely useless... like the fact that you quite literally cannot search for a post even if you type it in word for word means that all the classic, beloved, and infamous posts are these ephemeral things that only come around every so often and can only be found organically when they happen to make it to your dash like a flock of rare migratory birds

#you have to tag or index the posts you want manually
 #as god intended lol
 #this is partly why it's actually ok to tag your reblogs however you want
 #it's your filing system

Figures 17.1-17.2. User appreciation for Tumblr’s non-searchability and curated tagging.

The second use of tags as a commentary practice emerged because Tumblr initially lacked reply or comment features. Although replies now exist, expressive tagging endures as a core communication practice within the userbase. According to Stein (2017), “the use of

⁶ In fan communities, a “ship name” is a portmanteau of “relationship” between two characters, typically used to refer to a romantic or otherwise close relationship between them. These names are used by fans to identify and discuss their favorite romantic pairings, and are often popularized through fan fiction, fan art, and online discussions.

⁷ "Stucky" is a popular ship name in the Marvel Cinematic Universe (MCU) fandom, referring to the romantic or close relationship between Steve Rogers (Captain America) and Bucky Barnes (the Winter Soldier)

⁸ "FirstPrince" typically refers to a popular slash ship (fan fiction pairing) between Alex Claremont-Diaz and Prince Henry from the *Red, White & Royal Blue* fandom.

tagging with fandom-specific or even user-specific hashtags that only a select few would even know how to search ... had carve[d] out a private-in-public for fandom on Tumblr” (89). Hyper-specific and expressive tags help users create zones of address within public interest-based communities (fandom, social justice, mental health) where the tag space becomes a site of personal engagement (Figure 18). While users can obviously comment in the reblogs, the style and intention of that engagement often shift depending on the perceived tone, aesthetic form, and emotional stakes of the post. Reblogs tend to amplify, escalate, or transform posts publicly. At the same time, users frequently turn to the tag field to register their affective reception of the post without disrupting the post’s visible structure. Rather than a binary, Tumblr users navigate each post’s affective and aesthetic cues and decide when to step onto the stage through reblogs and when to whisper on the stage in tags.

#rwr #lgbtq culture
 #that book gives me so much queer joy as a panromantic mess
 #like. that book is "pure" validation #could not recommend it more
 #media recommendations
 #the whole bisexuality exploration arc Alex gets is just "chef's kiss"

Figure 18. User discussing *Red, White & Royal Blue* (2019) book.

Users often describe tags as their “footnotes,” “director’s commentary,” or “space for secret thoughts,” revealing how tags function as a liminal space: public yet intimate for personal testimonies (Figures 19.1-19.3). Tags often hold deeply personal reactions, including negative or vulnerable emotions. This has generated subgenres such as “vent posts” (Brett and Maslen 2021, Figure 20). Frieder views personal testimonies found in the vernacular practice of tagging through the metaphor of wetness: “Wetness is informational connectivity; it can also be called a smooth space, virality, plasma, sublimity, or just simply, dreaming ... a feeling when you read a poem that makes your brain shortwire” (2025, 27). Tags are an example that suggests reading practice on Tumblr opposes what Felski (2008) calls the dryness of detached critical reading. Rather, tags have become a fluid, networked form of meaning-making driven by affect. Tumblr tags, when read through the notion of wetness, are a fragmentary performance of feeling. They are not just critical interpretations of reblogged posts but involve the affective intensity of recognition, enchantment and knowledge towards media attachments, which we will also see in Tumblr-native practices like web weaving.

tags? those are my footnotes

going back to op's blog to see the directors commentary in the tags

I love tumblr tags so much. Like okay here's the main post and here's my little secret thoughts and addendums for the besties

Figure 19.1–19.3. User imaginaries of tagging practices.

#(ooc) #(tbd) #sudden real talk but #its been so... h a r d ... #just so hard
 #to feel anything #ive been so tired #everyone is so tired #all the time
 #everywhere. everyone is exhausted. we dont want to feel anything and those who
 want to feel passion again for life can't muster it
 #the world is full of death and sadness and despair lately and its exhausting
 #ive got this stuffed so deep into my chest that i feel congested #so yes.....
 #just #listens to people who real talk hardcore to make myself feel something
 #if only momentarily #because honestly thats #enough for now
 #a little reminder that its possible #a little break from the exhaustion and nihilism
 #and idk why i went off about this just
 #im feeling things about life and humanity and existentialism again for the first time in
 a long time and ! clap emoji tbh

Figure 20. Vent post featuring personal testimonials. Source: Brett and Maslen 2021

3.3.3 Pseudonymity, Tumblr Literacies, and Algorithmics (or Lack Thereof)

The feature of pseudonymity is central to the vernacular practice of personal testimonies. As Rose (2025) notes, “Tumblr’s position as a site of unusual attention to user privacy and pseudonymity, alongside its cultivated brand of community-mindedness, has led to users interpreting it as safer than and fundamentally disparate from other social media and blogging sites” (32). Tumblr’s pseudonymous design enables users to adopt aliases and conceal their real-life identities, allowing for a broader and more vulnerable form of self-expression. This is a particularly crucial consideration for what McCracken et al. call “counterpublics”—marginalized communities including LGBTQIA+ users, people of colour, sex workers, activists, disabled individuals, and feminist and queer fans (2020, 2). By de-emphasising authorship through reblogging and tagging, Tumblr fosters a culture where such voices are not only heard but given centre stage. The result is a counterpublic space where users participate in fan discourse and affirm their identities.

Fandom on Tumblr thrives within this pseudonymous environment. As Chew (2018) asserts, fans “used Tumblr, although it is technically a public platform, as this sort of private, informal space because they believed it to be a space not as carefully tracked by industries and the mainstream public.” In an era of increasing surveillance, monetization, and co-opting of fan spaces by media industries, Tumblr since 2020 continues to function as a liminal public/private space—a “dead” website still alive for fandoms. Belonging in fandom is a fuzzy concept, but one can start joining a fandom on Tumblr by reblogging, following tags, or posting about personal interests. The website’s relative anonymity, along with these vernaculars of personal testimonials and social curation, heightens the intimacy of being a fan in these interest-affinity spaces. This intimacy, for McCracken (2017), had made Tumblr “an alternative, tuition-free classroom, a powerful site of youth media literacy, identity formation,

and political awareness that often reproduces cultural studies methods of media analysis ... [and] collapses the boundaries between affect and social critique, leveling cultural hierarchies of ‘quality’ regarding media products” (152). Tumblr fandoms are a pedagogical playground that encourages users to play with the frames of narratives in media texts and the industrial value they create in media industries through their imaginative engagement. Users read and reinterpret media texts through their fannish pleasures/hatred, personal stakes, and communal participation on Tumblr. The meta-Tumblr post (Figure 21) demonstrates this fannish mode of engagement, transforming casual content into humorous moments of knowledge production sparked by niche passions. Tiidenberg et al. (2021, 59) understand this broader vernacular mode of participation within this multifandom culture through Tumblr’s “multimodal multiliterate affective literacies”, encompassing video and audio remixing, queer readings, socio-political ‘social justice’ critique, ironic humour, and forms of testimonial self-expression.

A big reason I can prob never truly quit Tumblr is this is the only website where I can read

[goof joke post about, say, Scandanavian geese]

[witty rejoinder]

followed by "Actually? I'm an ornithologist specializing in the migratory patterns of three specific species of geese over the Scandanavian peninsula, here's a genuinely fascinating short essay about a highly specific field of work and study, I took quite a lot of time out of my day to write this just because I wanted to share my passion, you're welcome"

it rules

Figure 21. Tumblr’s multimodal literacies enabled by reblogs.

Given this context, it is unsurprising that long-time Tumblr users often resist the platform’s recent algorithmic personalisation updates. The “For You” tab and Tumblr Blaze (a paid promotion feature) indicate growing algorithmic influence and monetization on Tumblr. While opt-outs exist to prevent abandoning the userbase, they signal the platform’s shift toward engagement metrics and attention economies in a moment of platform capitalism. Users mock these algorithmic features rather than engage with them, revealing a tension between user culture and platform incentives (Figure 22.1). In one Tumblr post (Figure 22.2), a user critiques algorithmic randomness in contrast to the curated intimacy of the “Following” tab, imbued with niche interests and interest-affinities with other Tumblr users. This is why Tumblr has a strong anti-clout and anti-influencer culture as the user base values the platform’s ethos of intimacy, creativity, and niche community-building over virality (Figure 22.3). Fame through follower counts or monetization, in fact, often invites ridicule rather than aspiration. For users, Tumblr is prized not for its potential to make someone a brand, but for its refusal to demand one. In this way, Tumblr fandoms thrive

because of pseudonymity and 'counterpublic fan culture, not in spite of it; as fandoms are formed via affective investments in media texts shared using reblogged posts, not personalized algorithms or influencer marketing.

"Why are you still on tumblr, it's a dead site"
 Tumblr is the ONLY site that still works in the way of -Follow this person, see their posts- instead of -you stopped scrolling and stayed on this post for .2 seconds longer than others, here's 100 more posts like it-
 I hate algorithms. Tumblr has its many issues. But at least I keep my choice of what I see.

Figure 22.1. Mockery of algorithmic design of platforms.

the "for you" page emoji being a crystal ball is very appropriate considering how it consistently fails to show me content relevant or accurate to my interests and torments me with horrifying visions instead

the "following" page emoji being a heart is also very appropriate because i love you all 🧡💕

Figure 22.2. User expressing distaste for 'For You' page.

all articles about tumblr's "decline" boil down to 2 things: you can't get famous on here and you can't make money on here. And they don't get that that's why we like it here.

Au contraire! You can absolutely get famous here

It is however, explicitly a bad thing.

You get put in the stock and laughed at by the citizens of tumblr town

Figure 22.3: Users discuss Tumblr's anti-clout and anti-influencer culture

3.4 Affective Counterpublics and Their Discontents Under Platform Capitalism

The pseudonymous counterpublic fan culture of Tumblr, with its playful multimodal literacies for fan interpretations, can also be a double-edged sword. While pseudonymity flourishes interest-based affinities that bring fans together over media texts, it can also limit accountability in fan discourses. McCracken et al. (2020) point out how “the same ‘call out culture’ and social justice rhetoric (often called ‘the Discourse’) that has served to check privilege and critique social hierarchies on Tumblr can be and often is weaponized to hurt, ridicule, and dehumanize others” (11). Fans are often morally policed or pathologized for liking “problematic” characters or offering controversial interpretations (Figure 23). In affective Tumblr fandom economies, emotions are ‘sticky’ culturally circulated expressions of value and thus, they are moralized and regulated by Tumblr fan community norms. These expectations force users to assess how their fannish pleasures and opinions will be read by others, resulting in self-surveillance where some readings are socially validated while others are delegitimized.

The phrase “media literacy is dead on Tumblr” can be primed as an example of delegitimization. It is often invoked as a defensive shield by white fans and Western-centric fandoms to dismiss the affective readings by fans of colour. As one user criticizes (Figure 24), affective readings by fans of colour that critique source texts are pathologized as overreactions or framed as lacking critical thinking. What is labeled as a lack of “media literacy” here is, in fact, a form of racialized regulation of emotions that excludes non-dominant reading experiences. As Lamerichs (Jenkins 2019) discusses in an interview with Jenkins, affective reading has long been dismissed as a fallacy in literary studies. But the policing of affective fan reading practices requires acknowledging that “fans are not stigmatized, emotions are” (2019). These two examples of affective dynamics on Tumblr fandoms—moral policing by fellow fans and racialized pathologization by dominant fandoms—may seem contradictory. But together they map the fault lines within the affective counterpublics by exposing how Tumblr’s affective fandom economies can reinforce hierarchies over whose affective readings are seen as legitimate, and whose are deemed “problematic.”

i really wish simple things weren't so complicated within fandoms. a character can be problematic but interesting. a character can make a mistake but not be evil. a character can hold a position of authority and still be a victim. a character doesn't have to be perfect and pure and innocent to be a victim. a character doesn't have to be perfectly pure for you to like them. liking a character who's fucked up doesn't mean you support their every action. why is this so complicated

Figure 23. User critique of moral policing for liking ‘problematic’ characters.

"Media literacy is dying!" And it's in response to fans of color voicing how a particular media is racially insensitive, or how being in fandom can carry trials because you'll be harassed by a majority of yte fans for calling out this behavior. Like, maybe you just missed the point, but sure it's media literacy dying that's the problem.

Figure 24. 'Media Literacy is dying!' weaponized for pathologizing fans of color

In Tumblr's 'culture of feels,' emotions, then, are not just an interpretive mode of fan reception; they are a kind of cultural currency, something to be exchanged, negotiated and even earned through socially acceptable affective readings to participate in fan communities. Crucially, Tumblr also profits from this affective fandom economies as "binding together the technology's protocols for interaction, content, and community with user's affective associations and experiences is a key way Tumblr generates revenue" (McCracken et al. 2020, 25). This process is part of what we know as platformization. If fans play with the narrative frames of media texts through transformational fanworks, they are also played by media industries within platform capitalism. This is the overarching theme of *Playing Fans: Negotiating Fandom and Media in the Digital Age* by Paul Booth (2015) who argues that "playing fandom isn't just what we do with our everyday media; it's also what our media do with us ... as [fan] creative work is used to sell products and services. Our clicks become capital. We are commoditized from and marketed to" (1). All too often, scholarship on both peak Tumblr years (McCracken et al. 2020; Tiidenberg et al. 2021; Cho 2022) and its post-2018, out-of-the-spotlight years has cast fan activities primarily as resistant responses to dominant media ideologies, reading transformative fan practices as inherently subversive. But these arguments paint an incomplete picture, especially when fans are only positioned as such through the alchemy of academic analysis that is still hellbent on proving fans as savvy interpreters, continuing the tradition of early fan studies, particularly Jenkins's *Textual Poachers* (1992), which worked hard to redeem fandom from its "fanatic" image. Yet today, fandom is no longer the scandalous subculture it once was; with the rise of digital fandoms, it is becoming increasingly mainstream (Booth 2015, 15).

Even as fan content gains mainstream visibility, fans remain bound by the platformed conditions of digital fan communities. Stein and Busse (2009) describe this as "limit play," where fans interact not only within the boundaries of media texts but also within the constraints of technological infrastructures and communal fandom expectations—as we just saw in Tumblr's fan culture. Platformization has only made these limitations more glaring, and fandom, while becoming mainstream, is still marginalized in relation to the dominance of media industries under platform capitalism. As De Kosnik (2013) reminds us, drawing on Terranova, fandom constitutes a form of "free labor": "Users keep a site alive through their labor, the cumulative hours of accessing the site (thus generating advertising), writing messages, participating in conversations, and sometimes making the jump to collaborators."

(Terranova 2000, 49). In more recent work, Terranova (2022) expands on the concept of digital labor, describing the digital platform economy as “an economy of the socialization of ideas, affects and percepts, and hence an economy of automated technosocial production and cooperation” (75). Tumblr stands as something of an anomaly within this corporate platform complex. Unlike Meta, Google, Amazon, or Microsoft, platforms that extract labor, data, attention, and presence through algorithmic governance and ad-driven models, Tumblr’s monetization strategy relies on affective user labour without strict algorithmic optimization and hypertargeted ad revenues. While Tumblr is not counter-hegemonic, its resistance to full automation and its user culture’s lobbying against algorithmic governance position the platform as neither wholly complicit with nor entirely resistant to the rapacious extractivism of platform capitalism. As a non-mainstream fannish platform in 2025 considered ‘dead’ by popular imagination, Tumblr exists within platform capitalism but remains at its periphery compared to larger platforms like Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Discord hosting fan content. Tumblr currently profits through the circulation of affective value. To use Cho’s (2015) term, it continues to “trade in affect.” The platform’s design, affordances, and vernacular practices work in tandem to produce a media environment animated by fan desire. Tumblr blogs function as “little databases”, where affect is iterable, tradeable, and archivable, generating cultural capital for fan communities, which in turn generates value for the platform itself.

3.5 A Bed, A Diary, A Museum: Blogs as ‘Little Databases’

In Tumblr’s pseudonymous architecture, users post, reblog, and tag media texts in ways that continuously reinscribe affective value. This affective value fuels Tumblr’s fandom economy by keeping users engaged in vernacular practices—social curation, personal testimonies, and interest-based community participation through multimodal literacies—and steers user blogs into what Snelson (2025) calls “little databases.” Defined as hands-on archival systems shaped by experimental, user-defined curatorial logics, little databases “reconfigure the contemporary experience of historical artifacts and thus transfigure each work in turn ... dramatically rematerializ[ing] historical works for the use and reuse of millions of contemporary users” (Snelson 2025, 7). Snelson goes on to examine small-scale non-institutional digital archives that are not merely digitisation projects, but digital archival systems that transform media texts, granting them renewed material and cultural life. As I have shown in the earlier section, transformation and rematerialization are all very good ways to describe the participatory culture of Tumblr, involving reinterpretation and reworking of cultural materials.

Snelson proposes that because ‘little databases’ exceed traditional archival aims of retrieval or searchability, they demand close reading rather than big data methods. Reading against the ‘digital turn’ in archival studies that increasingly favours large-scale computational analysis, Snelson argues that the transformative and rematerialization features

of the ‘little database’ need to be closely examined for interpreting the curatorial impulse embedded within these archives. Mandolessi (2023) also advocates for the need for close reading of the database as a narrative form: “Through the database, users can create their own narrative projects by remixing and hybridizing narrative segments from search results” (1520). In the case of Tumblr blogs, the relevance of this approach becomes clear very easily. While each blog includes a built-in archive page (accessible via username.tumblr.com/archive), it reveals little without attention to the user’s curatorial approach.

A close reading of each Tumblr blog can reveal how users constantly materialize and rematerialize their affective engagements with media texts through the practice of social curation. Users often self-identify as curators and describe their blogs as an extension of self in metaphorical terms (Figures 25.1-25.7): as a “bed” where other users are observers and occasional participants of their monologues; a “personal museum” of their inner lives, meticulously arranged yet unfiltered; a substitute for the ‘diary’; a space where they perform the role of a chaotic narrator; or a ‘public-private place’ where they can perform their personal identity. The blog database is a “journal” where users record and narrativize their reading experiences through fanworks, which feels “like adding a sticker to a journal” (Figure 25.7). It becomes a space where media texts are rematerialized not as static artifacts, but as curatorial objects with personal user narratives. One must also closely trace how a user reblogs content and organises tags to make sense of their blog’s narrative. Although some tagging practices reflect shared community vocabularies within fandom culture, many users develop their own tagging folksonomies (as in Figure 16). This is why blogs as ‘little databases’ require understanding of each user’s interests to know the kind of content they reblog and tag, thus demanding slow, contextual reading rather than quantitative methods alone to study blog databases. Ultimately, the collective imaginary of the Tumblr blog pulses with an archival impulse, an intimate database where users curate and perform their self-expression.

tumblr isn't a social media it's actually my bed and u all are my plushies watching me talk to myself

having a tumblr blog is like being the curator of my own personal museum of mental breakdowns and special interests

having a tumblr blog is for those of us who could never manage to keep a diary for more than two weeks when we were twelve

i hope my blog feels like you're walking through a really well-curated museum except there's this guy next to you who's talking on the phone and saying really insane things and you just have to deal with that

this app is literally my public private place to talk to myself

not now, mom i have to go on to tumblr dot com to reblog the gifs of the blorbos from my shows, archive my mental breakdowns after reading a devastatingly a tragic ending of two characters with the homoerotic subtext trope, spend time in the scrollable void to find gay fics recommendations to fix that and spam my mutuals with my hyperfixations

the best thing about tumblr is that you can watch a show and then you come here and someone has made a gifset of it and you can put it on your blog like a sticker in a journal

Figures 25.1-25.7. The shared imaginary of Tumblr as an archival space.

Tumblr blogs, as ‘little databases’, belong to the ontology of the digital archive. According to Mandolessi (2023), the database governs the organisation and access of digital objects in a digital archive where information is organised through the abstraction of certain units defined beforehand ... [and] the relationship between these units grants us access to the system of meaning” (1519). In the case of Tumblr blogs, these units aren’t always structured categories; rather, information on blogs is curated by registers of affect or ‘feels’. So, when you scroll a blog or explore its tag system, you’re navigating a curated, user-generated collection where meaning is organised through their affective reception of Tumblr posts in reblogs and organized through tag-based folksonomies. This resonates with Cho’s poetics (2015) of the Tumblr blog: “You are the sum of your posts, which are a visualization of your connections to others—a porous, living assemblage” (45). Mandolessi also evokes the idea of ‘assemblage’ as an essential trait of the digital archive to account for “the human and non-human actors that make up the dynamics, practices and procedures” that sustain these archival practices. My study of Tumblr’s platform architecture and culture captures how users’ affective reception towards texts circulates both ephemerally and timelessly, memorialized and re-memorialized in the network of blogs. As Rose writes on Tumblr, “each user incorporates their own memory, and then it is shared, and then it is remembered, and then it is shared—and so it continues, networked memory between networked selves” (51). Tumblr, then, needs to be examined as an archive of feelings, where this network of databases collectively converges to a platform-wide, affect-driven archival network.

3.6 Platformed Archive of Feelings

Tumblr is a digital, platformed archive of users’ ‘feels’. Unlike traditional, static repositories, digital archives are archives in motion, “where meaning arises not from singular curated narratives but from a dynamic, contingent multiplicity” (Mandolessi 2023, 1524). This multiplicity allows content to be continually recontextualized, remixed, and re-searched.

Through her case studies on fanfiction archives like *Archive of Our Own*, Abigail De Kosnik (2016) argues that digital technologies become archival not inherently, but through the labour and intention of “self-appointed, mostly nonprofessional individuals and collectives who regard some digital cultural productions and events as worth preserving” (62). This labour is democratizing, as it allows marginalized cultural artefacts—often excluded from institutional archives—to be preserved and circulated. Yet, to call something a democratizing archive does not imply utopia or an “absolute archive, that is to say, a perfect memory ... without any loss shown.” (Baetens and Van Looy 2007, 17). Such an archive would not only erase the nature of memory altogether but strip away the primary purpose of the archive, that is, the act of selection and curation of an interpretive subjectivity that narrativizes cultural memory. On Tumblr, the curation of subjectivities occurs through registers of affect generated by user activity on their blogs.

Ann Cvetkovich takes the notion of a dynamic archive a step further with her concept of ‘an archive of feelings.’ In this notion of archive that Cvetkovich assembles in her eponymous book, archives serve to record and communicate queer feelings as well as evoke feelings of recognition and compassion for its users: To preserve “the many forms of love, rage, intimacy, grief, shame, and more that are part of the vibrancy of queer cultures”. Tumblr, as several scholars have noted (Stein 2017, Cho 2015, McCracken et al. 2020, Tiidenberg et al. 2021), is a platform where fan communities and queer communities significantly overlap. Queer readings are often steeped in fan reception, often imbued with queer affect. But this isn’t to say all fannish affect is queer affect. Rather, Tumblr’s transformational reading practices “support forms of affective, erotic, and personal living that are public ... and sustained through collective activity” (Cvetkovich 2003, 9). Even when not explicitly queer, Tumblr’s vernaculars—emotional authorship, testimonial confessionality, and profane, hyperbolic humour—still echo Cvetkovich’s queer cultural codes of preserving feelings in public through fan reading practices. Since Tumblr, as a platformed digital archive, is constantly evolving, fan feelings become the medium through which cultural memory is both felt and made. The act of reading media (whether through memes, textposts, GIFs, or web weaving) creates a public yet personal record of affective reception. The blog then becomes a node in Tumblr’s networked archive, where the fan’s identity is shaped by the affective traces they leave behind in their blog. By preserving fans’ reading experiences, Tumblr constitutes an ‘archive of feelings’ that captures those discrete moments when users are moved by intimacy, hatred, love, rage, grief or shame in their media reception.

3.7 Archontic Texts in the Tumblr Archive

Cvetkovich (2016) emphasizes the role of popular culture in the ‘archive of feelings,’ where people document their emotional lives through public engagements with media texts. De Kosnik (2016) extends this idea through her concept of metaphorical archives: “archives that are opened up by each media text put into circulation, archives that audience members

enter into, plunder for usable material, and then augment and expand when they deposit their transformations and variations back into the archive of the source” (17). She calls these processes of preservation and transformation ‘archontic productions’, where fan creations continuously build upon and transform the source text. To recapitulate for the reader, De Kosnik (2016) argues that fans treat media texts as open-ended archives—selecting, extracting, and reworking parts of those texts that speak to their own identities, desires, and interpretations for their own fanwork creations. She attributes the rise of archontic productions like fanfiction, fanart, memes, and fan edits to the growing popularity of a digital remix culture.

I postulate that what emerges from these archontic productions in the age of digital hyperconnectivity is a fragmentary mode of engagement: a reading practice in which fans do not approach media texts as unified wholes, but as repositories from which specific fragments (scenes, quotes, character dynamics) are extracted for networked self-expression on Tumblr. These practices are less about retelling the entire source text and more about interpreting the moments in these source texts that move fans.

De Kosnik’s theory of archontic productions also considers the role of archival genres in the digital age. Eicchorn (2008) understands ‘archival genres’ as texts composed of elements collected from other texts, such as commonplace books in the Renaissance era and blogs in the contemporary era. De Kosnik wholeheartedly concurs with Eicchorn’s understanding of a blog as an archival genre, a collection of quotations of media authored by others (2016, 337). Rose (2025) also applies Eichhorn’s ideas to position web weaving as a contemporary archival genre, akin to the poetics of sentiment albums and commonplace books that “come[s] into being largely through taking from other sources rather than producing original material, organised in a meaningful, and often personal, structure” (44). While Rose doesn’t fully address the fragmentary nature of web weaving, I argue that it is precisely this fragmentary nature of web weaving that crystallizes web weaving as both an archontic production and a product of Tumblr’s platformed archive of feelings.. The reblogging culture of multiplicity, intimate tagging practices, the pseudonymous architecture and the distaste for algorithmic design and its archival environment can be a starting point to explain why web weaving as an archontic production is quintessentially a native practice to Tumblr. Within this platformed archive of feelings, web weaving emerges as a living assemblage of images, quotes, and excerpts often curated to memorialize personal reading experiences.

In the chapter that follows, I look into web weaving as a digital-born, fragmentary fan reading practice that embodies the form of archontic production. The disparate media fragments in web weaving often converge through shared emotional and thematic threads. Readers who engage in web weaving arrange media fragments in a collage-like form through their affective reception. Yet, these playful reading experiences are shaped by the limits of

Tumblr's affective fandom economies, which are themselves entangled with platform capitalism. As Tumblr monetizes user engagement and affective labour within an attention economy, certain emotions, especially those coded as queer, melancholic, and vulnerable, and texts aligned with Western-centric literary aesthetics circulate more widely, accruing cultural capital. As a result, I argue that web weaving is a critical point of insight into the fragmentary reading culture and platformization of fan culture in the digital age.

Chapter 4 Web of Fragments: Web Weaving as a Fragmentary Fan Reading Practice

“What is a quote? A quote (cognate with quota) is a cut, a section, a slice of someone else’s orange. You suck the slice, toss the rind, skate away. Part of what you enjoy in a documentary technique is the sense of banditry. To loot someone else’s life or sentences and make off with a point of view, which is called “objective” because you can make anything into an object by treating it this way, is exciting and dangerous. Let us see who controls the danger.” — Anne Carson (2005)

4.1 The Fragment, Fragmentary and Fragmentation

Readers who begin this thesis with the expectation of learning solely about contemporary reading practices in digital fan culture may instead encounter a more insistent subject—if not the true protagonist of this study—the fragment. ‘Fragment’ has become a central, if occasionally overused, refrain of this work, capturing not only the nature of web weaving but also the broader condition of reading in the digital age. Derived from the Latin *fragmentum*, meaning “a broken piece,” the fragment has etymologically long been associated with both rupture and potential, with what remains and what might be reassembled. Thus, making it an especially generative leitmotif for thinking about the aesthetics and affects of reading on Tumblr through web weaving.

This brings me to one of the inherent tensions that runs through the thesis: the interrelated but distinct concepts of the fragment, the fragmentary, and fragmentation. Fragment refers to the discrete unit (quote, image, scene, lyric) plucked from a larger whole. Fragmentary describes something consisting of fragments, as seen in the compositional logic of web weaving. Fragmentation signals the broader condition of digital hyperconnectivity that splinters reading experiences across platforms, texts, and multimodal expressions of digital ‘content’. Web weaving, I argue, is a fragmentary form: a curated juxtaposition of fragments that is both a condition and catalyst of the contemporary reading culture transformed by platformization and fragmentation in digital hyperconnectivity.

Freya Gowrley’s *Fragmentary Forms: A New History of Collage* (2024) offers a useful historical framework to contextualize the fragmentary form of web weaving. Gowrley is preoccupied with telling an expansive but not boundless art history of collage, going beyond our traditional understanding of collage as a modernist practice of cut-and-paste originating with Cubists Picasso and Braque. Instead, she pays attention to an array of fragmentary forms whose creative impulses are often imbued with feminist sensibilities in collage making. While Gowrley does not spend time discussing the differences between

collage and montage, I believe web weaving inherits the broader aesthetic sensibility collage rather than montage. Web weaving neither has what Manovich (2001, xxiv) critiques as the Fordist sequentiality of temporal cinematic montage, nor does it particularly aim for simultaneous perception found in spatial montage. The fragmentary logic of web weaving is not cinematic but curatorial; not necessarily temporal but relational. Thus, it aligns more with aesthetics of hybridity found in the culture of collage that has re-emerged in the computational culture as “the ‘cut-and-paste’ command, the most basic operation one can perform on digital data” (Manovich 2001, xxxi). In Gowrley’s work, collage is then considered a literal manifestation of things made of other things, across cultures and geographies. The beautifully illustrated and extensively documented forms, genres, styles and materials of fragmentary forms such as quilts, scrapbooks, herbaria, sentiment albums, valentines, also opened my eyes to the multiplicity of cultural functions of collage. These functions resist reductive classification, as each collage is borne out of distinct production and consumption conditions. My argument on web weaving has earmarks of one particular function of collage as a “powerful communicant of the desires and devotions of its makers. As such, we might read its pages in relation to an extensive cache of scrapbooks, albums, and commonplace books made by familial units and groups of friends” (Gowrley 2024, 202). Web weaving reanimates these collage styles, impregnated with registers of desire and devotion. The selection and curation of media fragments as a form of labour in web weaving are most often expressions of personal desires and attachments shared within groups of fannish and bookish Tumblr communities.

Scholars have already caught on to the kinship of web weaving with some of the collage forms discussed by Gowrley. In his work, Rose (2025) is besotted with the idea of web weaving/parallel posts as “a digital remediation of the collage manuscript form, most poignantly that of the commonplace book” (24). Although not discussing the subject of web weaving directly, Evan Hayles Gledhill (2018) has gestured towards the correlation between practices of fandom blogging on Tumblr and commonplacing, scrapbooking and curating sentiment albums. In a similar vein to Gowrley, he identifies these collage forms as marginalized feminist practices. My contribution to this emergent conversation is to position web weaving as a fan reading practice that involves interpreting, sharing and preserving personal sentiments found in intertextual encounters of reading within digital fan communities.

Gowrley ends her book with a meditation on digital collages: “A spread of visuals that resonate with groupings and juxtapositions on sites such as Pinterest, Tumblr, Instagram, and even Google images. Like the scrapbooks and collections ... compiled in the eighteenth century, these pages represent an attempt to ... categorize and organize the endless waves of content available online” (2024, 374). In extending her already expansive scope, this chapter focuses on Tumblr users’ dedication to the preservation of sentiment through web weaving,

which transforms fragments of media texts “into assemblages imbued with creativity and personal significance” in the platformed archival environment of Tumblr (Gowrley 2024, 173).

4.2 Genealogies and Genesis of Web Weaving

Let me begin by briefly tracing the genealogies of web weaving to earlier fragmentary fan practices on Tumblr. These fan practices also involve reading texts from various sources and assembling constellations of select fragments (quotes, images, movie stills) into new narratives. Moodboards (or pic sets), GIF sets, and fandom text post memes have been studied extensively in scholarship.

Moodboards are a collage of still images that are carefully curated to convey a sense of atmosphere, whether related to a specific character, narrative or visual style (Hautsch 2022). In Figure 26, we see a moodboard of still images created to convey the visual mood of a video game character. GIF sets have also been a significant subject of fan studies scholarship. Stein (2015) interprets them as “sets of images, sometimes animated, sometimes not, arranged in a grid of sorts to communicate as a whole” (n.p.). Evolving primarily on Tumblr due to its interface, GIF sets enable fans to juxtapose multiple visuals drawn from the same or related storyworlds. For example, the GIF set from the Thai drama *Bad Buddy* (2021) in Figure 27 traces the relationship arc of two queer characters, with a caption that highlights an affective reading of the characters’ relationship. Fandom text post memes are also a collage form that typically involves captioning screenshots of stills and GIFs from visual media texts, movies and TV series, with humorous texts obtained from different sources (Figure 28). These memes are fan interpretations that express felt truths about characters beyond the original narrative, and require familiarity with both the source text and distinct ironic Tumblr humour in this practice (Lowe 2020, 182–183). Tumblr’s archival and affective environment, due to its design, affordances and vernacular culture, can explain the evolution of these fragmentary forms of these practices. Fans fragment the source media text into parts and reassemble them into new non-linear and highly interpretive multimodal compositions. Web weaving belongs to the genealogy of these practices because it operates with the same logic of fragmentation that emerges through fan interactions with the technological and social ecology of Tumblr fan culture.

Barbatos, the Anemo Archon 🌬️

#venti #anemo archon #barbatos
#venti genshin impact
#genshin impact venti

Figure 26. Moodboard for Barbatos from the video game Genshin Impact (2020).

I don't want our future to change. *I still want you in my future.*

Figure 27. Ink and Pa (queer characters) GIF set from Bad Buddy (2021)

Figure 28. Part of *Bad Buddy* (2021) text post memes compilation.

Having identified web weaving within the lineage of Tumblr’s fragmentary fan practices, I will now outline a brief account of the genesis of web weaving to illustrate the practice as something emergent, not from a single user, but through a decentralized evolution within Tumblr’s literary quotation culture. In *A Library of Fragments: Digital Quotations, New Literacies, and Attention on Social Media*, Booten (2017) observes that Tumblr users devote significant attention to sharing the words of others through quotations. It also led to the platform introducing a dedicated “quote” post format as part of its multimedia flexibility (revisit Figure 8). This quotation culture on Tumblr laid the foundation for novel multimodal, curatorial, yet still fragmentary, practices to emerge. This broader quotation culture provides the necessary context for challenging one of the central claims in Rose’s work: web weaving rose alongside Dark Academia and “parallel posts are Dark Academia’s medium du jour” (Rose 2025, 12). This implication that the current expression of web weaving is retroactively understood within the Dark Academia subculture risks overstating the relationship between web weaving and Dark Academia by codifying web weaving as a subcultural aesthetic practice.

Dark Academia emerged on Tumblr in the mid-2010s as an internet subculture and later spread to Instagram, YouTube and TikTok during the COVID years (Adriaansen 2022). According to the *Internet Aesthetics Wiki*, a collaboratively edited repository documenting internet aesthetics-cum-subcultures, Dark Academia centres on classic literature, self-discovery, and a romanticized pursuit of knowledge (“Dark Academia,” n.d.). This community-authored description reflects how the subculture understands itself. In scholarly discussions, Rose draws on Murray (2023, 352), who characterizes the aesthetic as a “fatalistic cosplay” of “academic self-fashioning” (Rose, 108). As an academic-based subculture, it also formed a shared fandom around media texts with tragic storylines like Donna Tartt’s *The Secret History* (1992), *Dead Poets Society* film (1989), and classical works such as *The Iliad*, Mary Shelley’s *Frankenstein* (1818), and Oscar Wilde’s *The Picture of Dorian Gray* (1890). It features Gothic motifs, Neo-Gothic architecture and libraries, Greek and Latin vocabulary lists, vintage school-inspired fashion, and curated moodboards that stylize a reverence for books often to the point of fetishism that Pressman (2020) describes as contemporary “bookishness.” While this aesthetic culture helped popularize certain web weaving posts, the connection is more incidental than intrinsic. Even the *Internet Aesthetics Wiki* notes that web weaving “is not exclusive to Dark Academia and is more aligned with fans of literature in general” (n.d.). I would take this further to argue that web weaving aligns more broadly with fans of media texts attuned to the participatory and fragmentary conditions of Tumblr’s quotation culture.

A closer look at the origins of this practice supports my view. The most recognizable form of web weaving, the vertical sequential collage (Figure 4), is often attributed to having been invented by Tumblr user @oumaimas. However, as Rose (2025) also clarifies, this direct attribution is incorrect (10). As with many native Tumblr practices, web weaving was borne out of the decentralized process of collective circulation, iterative reblogging and the rise of quotation culture across overlapping fannish and bookish communities. Even before the tag #web weaving gained traction, posts that brought together fragments around a shared thematic resonance in the wake of the quotation culture were already circulating under tags like #parallels, #comparatives, and #compilations. However, what distinguishes @oumaimas’s contribution is the coining of the tag #web weaving, which caught on within Tumblr’s culture. She describes web weaving most notably in her widely circulated Medium essay on Tumblr:

I have filled what little empty hours I have with images and song and poetry, weaving a web that rests upon tenderness itself, tending to the images growing within me. Web weaving is delicate work, spinning around one single idea, the work of others and my own love, but they map roads towards one another. (Oumaimas 2019)

Here, user @oumainas gestures toward the intertextual impulse of readers like herself who observe and connect seemingly unrelated texts through a shared tenderness. This notion of ‘tenderness’ found in the reader’s love for the work of others allows me to frame web weaving as a phenomenon not exclusive to Dark Academia fandoms. But it is certainly apparent in the quotation culture that involves “a literate attention devoted not to any one text but scattered over or threaded among a multitude of textual fragments whose meaning and beauty can be grasped instantaneously” (Booten 2017, 2). By seeking to marry one fragment with another in the act of intertextuality, the beauty of web weaving lies not just in its connections, but also in how users make those connections visible.

The quotation culture on Tumblr, with the circulation of literary quotes originating from print media (novels, poets, and philosophers) has contributed to the fragmentation of reading in the digital age. Booten (2017) explores this cultural shift by examining the evolving identity of the reader in the digital age. Drawing on Michel de Certeau’s (1984, 174) metaphor of readers as nomadic “poachers” who tactically navigate texts authored by others, Booten argues that digital fan spaces like Tumblr enable readers to claim an “established place” from which they not only consume but also interpret, reinterpret, and circulate media. This blurring of production and consumption resonates with what Jenkins (1992), building on De Certeau, famously terms ‘textual poaching.’ While I do not dispute that fans are not just consumers but active producers who contribute to what De Kosnik (2016) calls “rogue archives”—user-driven repositories that preserve fan interpretations through archontic productions like fanfiction, fanart, and more—one might also argue that platforms like Tumblr, by offering an “established place” or ‘platformized place’ for fan activities, risk domesticating the anarchic nomadic freedom that once defined fan culture. In this chapter, I draw on Felski’s modes of engagement with literature to examine how the affordances and constraints of platformization on Tumblr determine how users read, interact with, and transform media texts through web weaving.

4.3 Web Weaving as Recognition of the Networked Self

Recognition has long been a fundamental desire behind reading. For Felski (2008), it is a form of engagement when a reader feels “addressed, summoned, called to account,” glimpsing traces of themselves in the pages they read (30). This intimate encounter reorients the reader’s sense of self through media reception. Borrowing Proust’s observation, she describes recognition as an old and enduring use of literature acknowledged in cultural history: “every reader is, while he is reading, the reader of his own self. The writer’s work is merely a kind of optical instrument which he offers to the reader to enable him to discern what, without this book, he would perhaps never have perceived in himself (Felski 2008, citing Proust, 32). Don Quixote’s reading of chivalric romances is a fitting example, because seeing oneself in a book becomes a route, sometimes the most direct route, back to oneself. Felski critiques how literary criticism, especially in its ideological and symptomatic roots, has

often dismissed recognition as politically naïve or complicit, accusing it of shoring up illusions of a coherent self and deflecting attention from the structures of race, class, gender, and power that render identity formation. She contends that the indisputable fact that the self is “socially constructed” does not suspend belief in our own selfhood. Recognition, then, is not inherently apolitical; rather, it is one of the affective forces that move readers through texts, complicating and enriching their sense of identity and relationality with the social world.

In the fragmentary fan practice of web weaving, readers begin by glimpsing themselves in diverse texts—films, books, lyrics, paintings—then become transformative fan-authors, creating multimodal collages in which others may also see themselves. Emerging from platformized digital fan culture, web weaving offers a mode of recognizing a ‘networked self’ within fragmentary reading experiences. Papacharissi (2018, 2) imagines the ‘network self’ by conceptualizing online social networks as stages for hybrid modalities of expression and connection, linking individuals to multiple audiences simultaneously. Platforms allow users to leave multimodal traces of their stories, inviting others to relate and repurpose them in acts of intertextuality. If seeing yourself in a text is a mirror, I think of seeing yourself in a digital-born text circulating on a platform as a mirror palace: reading shifts from a solitary reflection to a maze of glimmers, where one’s sense of self ricochets against others’ reflections. In this mirror palace, you not only recognize yourself in fragments, but witness others recognizing themselves in your creation, your recognition refracted through theirs.

This networked cycle begins with recognition as self-expression is wound through the idea of web weaving: “Sometimes I read something and it feels like plunging my cupped hands into my own secret soul and reaching” (Oumaimas 2019). The readerly feeling of reaching inside your soul through media reception is palpable in this web weaving (Figure 29), which collages moments of a daughter’s grief, parental absence, and longing for love through distinct but interlinked multimodal fragments. “It says, stay dad,” as the caption renders, shapes the act of recognition of a self formed, even sacrificed, for a father’s love. The visuals of embraces offer glimpses of parental affection and their eventual rupture. Textual excerpts like “He says she is his émerveillement he says he will never leave her, not in a million years” and “Last night I smoked a cigarette / my father would’ve been so upset” juxtapose idealized paternal love offering mythical promises with quiet rebellion and guilt that becomes painfully ironic. The lyric “I dreamed it for you, Dad / It wasn’t for me” ties the weave with resignation. Together, the intertextual connections made through these fragments help the reader, as the creator of this post, recognize parts of their own familial ache in the quiet grief of this post. This echoes in the self-disclosure within the tags: #im leaving home soon #time to watch interstellar #i feel like if you look at this web weaving page #you just learn i have abandonment issues and my parents aren’t in love. The curation of the web

weave summons (to use Felski’s term) the intensity of grief, making the reader’s affective reception of these media texts viscerally felt.

"Last night it had been my **father** who had finally said it, 'She's never coming home.' A clear and easy piece of truth that everyone who had ever known me had accepted. But he needed to say it, and she needed to hear him say it."

"He sweeps her hair back from her ears and he swings her above his head. He says she is his émerveillement, he says he will never leave her, not in a million years."

Last night I smoked a cigarette
 My dad would have been so upset

I had a dream
 I dreamed it for you, Dad
 It wasn't for me, Dad

"it says "stay," dad."
 // the lovely bones (alice sebold) // the mysterious benedict society // anthony doerr // interstellar // why am i like this (orla gartland) // the oa // rose's turn (glee) //
 #web weaving #father #dad #somethin #sad web weaving #idk #im leaving home soon #time to watch interstellar #you know #i feel like if you look at this web weaving page #you just learn i have abandonment issues and my parents arent in love
 #sorry about that #mine #the lovely bones #the mysterious benedict society #anythony doerr #interstellar #orla gartland #the oa #glee #tagging glee huh #hate my fucking life

Figure 29. A web weaving titled : “it says, “stay”, dad”.

The act of compiling what the user sees in these fragments is an act of transformative fan authorship. While transformative fan culture does not usually cling to the old Romantic ideal of the author as a singular genius whose intentions dictate the meaning of a work (the kind of author Barthes famously “declared dead”), the idea of the author comes across as a heuristic device—someone who frames interpretations without the ultimate authority of meaning (Dahlberg-Dodd 2019). This idea of authorship strikes at the core of De Kosnik’s (2016) ‘archontic productions’, which describe media text as ever-expanding archives, always open to new entries from readers who extract meanings from the archive for their own creations, which others then interpret, and the cycle of shared emotional authorship goes on. In web weaving, the novelty of fragmented reading lies not in recognition as a reading experience but in the networked structure of participation that invites readers to recognize and then become authors for their audiences by reblogging and tagging, thus reinterpreting through their experiences of recognition. These performances of self-expression are networked by the accumulation of affect across a web weaving post’s circulation. Consider a web weaving on sibling loss from a fan of television series *The Bear* (2022) (Figure 30.1). Another user, recognizing their own loss, reblogs it with tags marking their brother’s death anniversary: #i can’t breathe #it hurts so much (Figure 30.2). Through this reblog, the original post, rooted in the creator’s recognition of sibling grief, absorbs new layers of meaning. The grief it expresses now carries another person’s story, intertwining two affective experiences into a shared emotional text. The post shifts from solitary self-recognition to a networked self.

I had a brother who was my savior, made my childhood bearable.

CREON: Why did you try to bury your brother?

ANTIGONE: I owed it to him

I'm gonna lose my house.

Don't co-sign
for a drug addict.

CREON: Polynices was a rebel and a traitor, and you know it

ANTIGONE: He was my brother

I knew it was dumb
to co-sign, FYI.

i love when tragedies are like "the love was there. it didnt change anything. it didnt save anyone. there were just too many forces against it.

Hey

Please don't do this.

but it still matters that the love was there"

Figure 30.1. A web weaving for *The Bear* (2022): “Michael & Natalie Berzatto”

#it's the anniversary of my brother's death #i can't breathe
 #it hurts so much #the bear #web weaving #sibling loss #grief
 #poetry #quotes

Figure 30.2. A user's response to *The Bear* (2022) web weaving

Etymologically, recognition derives from Latin *recognoscere*, which means to literally “know again”. In web weaving, it becomes the transformative act of seeing oneself take shape in the polyphonic echo of others. When the process of recognition in reading moves beyond a private moment of “I see myself in this” to a public, networked form of identity work of “what do you see?”, web weaving becomes a performance of the networked self. Users reflect on their own lived experiences through the text of the web weaving. It creates a fertile ground for curatorial activism, “where lesser-known or radically different stories and histories are purposefully highlighted to decenter institutionalized racism, sexism, and homophobia” (Tiidenberg et al. 2021, 61). In Figure 31.1, the user assembles remnants of personal letters, photographs, poetry, and other fragments into a web of queer memory and feeling. Sources include McDarragh’s Stonewall photograph (1969), Joan E. Biren’s lesbian feminist photography (1978), intimate letters Sackville-West to Woolf, a literary quote from Sappho; a relic of a former lover who died of AIDS, preserved as the *Electric Fan* by John Boskovich (1997), the *Lovers of Modena* archaeological image of skeletons (2009), and user submissions to the counter-mapping queer platform of *Queering the Map*. While the web weaving gestures across temporalities to affirm queer presence, the tags epitomize its felt meaning: #so many of us. there’s so much history. #we aren’t alone (Figure 31.2). Another user reblogs this weave, reframing the metaphor of queer love as “drowning” into one of survival, of learning how to swim (Figure 30.3). Such readerly/authorly exchanges in web

weaving illustrate Felski’s claim that the value of recognition in literature helps women and minorities parse the complexities of personhood (2008, 33). Recognition, then, becomes preservation of affective reception through web weaving. To recognize oneself in a web weaving and to reblog and tag those posts as “this hurts,” “this is me,” “this is us”, is to embed affect into the database of your blog. The fan reading practice of web weaving is a mode of recognition that maps personal feelings onto a collage of media fragments, which are then preserved for others to encounter, identify with, and echo in the networked ‘archive of feelings’.

"And you have fixed my Life – however short. You did not light me: I was always a mad comet; but you have fixed me. I spun round you a satellite for a month, but I shall swing out soon, a dark star in the orbit where you will blaze... Someday, I must tell how we sang, shouted, whistled and danced through the dark lanes through Colinton; and how we laughed till the meteors showered around us, and we felt calm under the winter stars. And some of us saw the pathway of the spirits for the first time. And seeing it so far above us, and feeling the good road so safe beneath us, we praised God with louder whistling; and knew we loved one another as no men love for long."

– Letter from Wilfred Owen to Siegfried Sassoon, November 1917. (via [unhistorical](#))

Dear John,

I don't know why I have to tell you this today (but I do) — perhaps it's because when I look out into the fog all I can see is the hairs of your adorable chest. I'm terribly in love with you, and have been for such a long time, ever since the first time Frank took me to your apartment. I looked around at your beautiful paintings and suddenly everything I'd ever felt about you turned into a diamond or a rose or something — anyway I went striding up and down while Frank played Poulenc and felt exactly like the Ugly Duckling the day he found he was a swan.

Then you came home and I didn't think I could ever look at you or to you again, all I could do was giggle and snort and twitch. But I've looked at you a lot since then, and there isn't anybody else in the world I want to look at; or want, for that matter.

It seems to me that I've been so GOOD that I couldn't hate myself more. I don't see why I couldn't have been born a robber baron type instead of a fool.

Now I'm going down and set 57th Street on fire to keep you warm.

This is all nonsense. I love being in love with you, it makes even unhappiness seem no bigger than a pin, even at the times when I wish so violently that I could give my heart to science and be rid of it.

With all my love,

Jimmy

... I am reduced to a thing that wants Virginia. I composed a beautiful letter to you in the sleepless nightmare hours of the night, and it has all gone: I just miss you, in a quite simple desperate human way. You, with all your undumb letters, would never write so elementary a phrase as that; perhaps you wouldn't even feel it. And yet I believe you'll be sensible of a little gap. But you'd clothe it in so exquisite a phrase that it would lose a little of its reality. Whereas with me it is quite stark: I miss you even more than I could have believed; and I was prepared to miss you a good deal. So this letter is really just a

someone will remember us
I say
even in another time

there's so much love in the world. so much love you could drown in it.

Figure 31.1: A web weaving titled, "there's so much love in the world. so much love you could drown in it."

Fred W. McDarrah, outside the Stonewall Inn in June 1969 /
queering the map / Marie Ueda, "1977 San Francisco Gay Day
 Parade" / Wilfred Owen to Siegfried Sassoon / the Lovers of
 Modena / James Schuyler to John Button / John Boskovich,
 "Electric Fan (Feel it Motherfuckers): Only Unclaimed Item from
 the Stephen Earabino Estate" / Vita Sackville-West to Virginia
 Woolf / Joan E. Biren / Saphho, Fragment 147 / @orpheuslament,
 "The Second Coming, or Jesus at the Gay Bar"

#the number of times i almost cried making this
 #like guys there are so many of us. there's so much history.
 #we aren't alone. we've never been alone #web weaving
 #web weave #compilations #comparatives #parallels ... See all

Figure 31.2: Corresponding tags on the above web weaving.

We have always existed, and we always will. No matter how they try
 to drown us, we learn to swim.

Figure 31.3: Reblogged comment by a user on the above web weaving/

4.4 Dwelling in Enchantment: The Aesthetic Experience of Web Weaving

The fragmentary form of web weaving evokes a reading experience rife with enchantment. In Felski's (2008) terms, enchantment is a being "swept away" by media texts by being immersed in "an unusual intensity of perception and affect" (59). The intertextual and multimodal nature of web weaving conjures precisely this affect-laden reading experience, bringing the reader's perception to the forefront. Rose (2025) describes this immersion in web weaving as "a climactic form of dwelling—remembrance, rumination, and return to texts" (46). Each fragment in web weaving accumulates to amplify feelings like a spell cast over the reader. Tumblr's polyphony of tags and reblogs deepens this immersion, enabling users as networked selves to extend sentiments by making individual intertextual connections within a post. Many users (Figure 32.1-32.2) recount the experience of web weaving through metaphors of magic: It is a "magical art diary collage poem" that "inject[s] little alchemy into the scrolling day" by "build[ing] a dome ... of this one thing that so many people and perspectives have tried to name or express or memorialise." Rose (2023) argues that web weaving "represents a reclamation of poetry in the digital age" (2). I extend his argument by reading the aesthetic experience of enchantment in web weaving, using the concept of "poetic identity" (Mayer and Bourchardon 2020) in the digital environment.

#oh for real!!! #it's like a magical art diary collage poem
 #transcends everything mwah i love it

#intertextuality as connection. intertextuality as breathing context of the largest kind imaginable
 #if the page lays flat then these intertextuality posts make language 3D
 #build a dome of around me of this one thing that so many people and perspectives have tried to name or express or memorialise
 #intertext is as close as text can come to reality imo
 #and that type of post injects that little alchemy into the scrolling day. casual magic.

Figures 32.1-32.2. User experience of web weaving as magic and alchemy.

Poetic identity is fundamental to Tumblr users who practice web weaving. Mayer and Bourchardon (2020) propose that digital literature encourages forms of reading that eschew any sort of linearity, instead leaving the reader to interactively wander through a web of interlinked, constantly evolving digital fragments (or hypertexts) compiled by multiple authors. Their notion of poetic identity is marked by instantaneity and multiplicity. I use “poetic” here to describe this immersive, fragmentary mode of reading, where diverse perceptions, thoughts, and sensations converge in moments of affective intensities; rather than tying ‘poetic’ to any literary genre. In this model, reading is “a mosaic of instantaneous experiences” (Mayer and Bourchardon 2020), centered less on narrative continuity and more on the sensory and cognitive whiplash of the reader’s feelings as they encounter a rapid succession of impressions, images, and sounds. In the case of Tumblr, the poetic identity we build on our blog is a network of instantaneous experiences, expressed by multimodal reblogs, tags and posts, which then becomes readable like an archival collection to other readers. Mayer and Bourchardon suggest that the ways we fashion our identities online mirror the ways we read in digital spaces.

User expression is closely linked with the platform’s sociotechnical architecture, which in turn influences the reading practices like web weaving native to Tumblr fan culture. In Figure 33, for instance, a “When/And” genre of web weaving begins with a single quotation and grows through reblogs, each user adding another fragment. The resulting constellation draws on fragments by women artists of colour and/or queer writers speaking from the margins, building a mosaic of media reception that declares self-worth as resistance. Tumblr’s “yes–and” reblog culture makes each addition deeply intertextual, turning the act of weaving through reblogging akin to flipping through a communal internet poetry book. Readers are “pulled irresistibly into its orbit,” where self and text blur into an inchoate intermingling (Felski 2008, 59). In the networked platform of Tumblr, the gravitational pull of a Tumblr post draws the reader into a shared emotional authorship through reblogging, as fragments begin to circulate and accrue meaning. The networked self is constituted in part by the very fragments it selects, reblogs, and reframes. Web weaving turns reading into a poetic performance of the networked self dwelling in their reception through the act of collating

fragments. Rose (2023) puts it well: “the act of fragmentation becomes one of memorialisation, the curator absorbing the text into themselves” (13). The outpouring of poetic expression that I have read as enchantment thus allows the reader to preserve their affective reception of texts wound around a shared theme, like pollen gathered in the hive of web weaving.

when lizzo said “self love is survival” and when hannah gadsby said “do you understand what self-deprecation means when it comes from somebody who already exists in the margins? it’s not humility. it’s humiliation” and when mitski said “i used to rebel by destroying myself, but realized that’s awfully convenient to the world. for some of us our best revolt is self preservation”

when audre lorde said “caring for myself is not self-indulgence, it is self-preservation, and that is an act of political warfare”

when Jenny Slate tweeted, “As the image of myself becomes sharper in my brain&more precious, I feel less afraid that someone else will erase me by denying me love”

Figure 33. *When/And collaborative web weaving post.*

While I do share the sentiments of Mayer and Bourchardon (2020) that poetic identity is digital literary culture’s *du jour* due to the multiplicity and fragmentation of digital literary texts, I also believe the construction of reader’s identity has more often than not always been about sewing a patchwork of ideas, words, and imagery from people we speak to, people who inspire us and those we revere from afar. In Barthesian’s words, the text is after all a “tissue of quotations” (1986, 146). If the “magic” of intertextuality has always been central to the reading experience, then the globalized, platformized, multimodal digital landscape only intensifies and simultaneously capitalizes on this desire for reading. The circulation, contextualization, and recontextualization of fragments further disrupts binaries between author and reader, high and low art, and original and copy, but does not completely subvert them under platform capitalism.

Felski also challenges the persistent assumption that only “high art” can elicit complex aesthetic experiences of beauty and enchantment, while the enchantment experienced through popular culture is written off as the ideological condition of consumerism. She asks why an image in a museum “calls forth a rich range of aesthetic responses” but the same image in a magazine only “triggers a desire to buy more shoes” (2008, 70). Her critique exposes disciplinary biases rooted in class prejudice in literary studies that treat popular art as little more than an ideological tool, while elevating high art to

an almost theological status, a hierarchy that has often reinforced the separation of “art” from “culture.” (2008, 71). If enchantment is seen as an illusory form of control, typically associated with popular culture, she argues, then cultural studies should focus more closely on the affective dimensions of aesthetic experience in popular art to extend or challenge this view. But the discipline has more often than not persisted in portraying readers of popular media as “savvy interpreters” and “alert and critical consumers” (Felski 2008, 64). Henry Jenkins, a foundational scholar of the first wave of fan studies, affirms this disciplinary unease in linking theories of enchantment to fan studies. He recalls struggling as a first-generation fandom scholar to address fandom’s emotional dimensions, fearing that recognizing affect would reinforce stereotypes of fans as irrational (2019). Like many cultural studies subfields, fan studies is now taking an ‘affective turn,’ and here I discuss Tumblr users’ affective reading experiences through enchantment in the web weaving practice.

Tumblr users engaging in web weaving profess their love for how web weaving posts transverse high” and “low” culture, creating juxtapositions that invite enchantment precisely because of their fragmentary collage form (Figures 34.1–34.2). My study challenges early fan studies’ stigmatization of fans by centering their affective reading experiences. Getting absorbed in a web weaving post, whether weaving “high” art fragments or intertextual connections across these brows of culture (Figure 35), demonstrates that the affective dimension of fandom is not just valid but essential to understanding digital fan cultures today. Yet, as Lamerichs (2019) reminds us, affective reading does not exclude critical engagement: “Fans discuss and evaluate texts, remix, socialize, and immerse themselves deeply. All these practices go hand in hand, why should we be any different as academics?” After all, ‘Discourse’ remains a core, if not sacred, tenet of transformative fan culture on Tumblr. Yet, this discourse sometimes takes the ugly form of moral censorship within Tumblr’s progressive leftist counterpublics, where affective reading experiences and imaginative interpretations of readers are often policed and dismissed as “problematic” if they don’t align with prevailing notions of political correctness in fan communities. At the same time, many users critique these fan discourses themselves for failing to recognize the dominance of Anglophone media fandoms that complicate issues of access, class, race, and the broader dynamics of platform capitalism. As we’ll see, many users feel that Tumblr fans also reproduce cultural hierarchies by time and again failing to account for linguistic, economic, and racial barriers that impact the circulation of creative labour under platform capitalism.

*#especially when it's a mix of 'fine art' and 'basic' pop music etc like
 very different media*

#this is why tumblr is better than english class
#oh here it's creative and sexy
#but when i make bastille and/or shrek references in lit class it's
'derailing the discussion' and i need to 'stick to the source material'

Figures 34.1-34.2: Users on juxtaposition of high and popular culture in web weaving.

"It hurts to love. It's like giving yourself to be flayed and knowing that at any moment the other person may just walk off with your skin."

WHAT IS THE POINT OF LUKEWARM LOVE?
IF I AM NOT DROWNING IN IT I HAVE NO
DESIRE FOR IT

I'm in love. And this love is about to carry me off somewhere. The current's too overpowering; I don't have any choice. It may very well be a special place, some place I've never seen before. Danger may be lurking there, something that may end up wounding me deeply, fatally.

"the more you love
the more you suffer."

Either love is
 —A shrine?
 or else a scar.

*In this part of the story I am the one who
 dies, the only one, and I will die of love because I love you,
 because I love you, Love, in fire and in blood.*

"Find what you love
 and let it kill you."

*I love you more than my own skin and even though
 you don't love me the same way, you love me anyways,
 don't you? And if you don't, I'll always have the hope
 that you do, and I'm satisfied with that. Love me a
 little. I adore you.*

yeah, love hurts.

susan sontag || unknown poem || haruki murakami, sputnik
 sweetheart || 1927 children's book, jellyfish || vincent van gogh ||
 marina ivanova tsvetaeva, poem of the end || pablo neruda, 20 love
 sonnets and a song of despair || caitlin conlon, consider the hairpin
 turn || charles bukowski || frida kahlo

Figure 35. Web weaving post referencing Van Gogh, Susan Sontag, children's book, and contemporary poetry.

Web weaving itself reflects these cultural hierarchies and cannot fully subvert them. As Felski notes, capitalism may intensify our sense of the magical by “latch[ing] onto affective predispositions and human yearnings that long predate modern economic systems” (2008, 74). Web weaving expresses a poetic identity that yearns to dwell, connect, and be swept away in reading, but it cannot completely overturn hierarchies embedded in platform capitalism that profits from affective engagement. Therefore, I will now argue that the ways in which knowledge is organized and produced through web weaving are neither a “counter-canon” as Rose (2025) suggests nor a fully counterhegemonic practice as Frieder (2025) claims.

4.5 Is Web Weaving a Counter-Hegemonic Knowledge Structure?

What does reading help us know? Felski argues that it offers “the hope of gaining a deeper sense of everyday experiences and the shape of social life” (2008, 87). This question takes on renewed significance within Tumblr’s platformized fan communities, where meaning emerges not only from media texts themselves but from how fans perform, reinterpret, and re-author them through fan reading practices like web weaving. On Tumblr, these practices constantly shape and reshape how knowledge is organized, produced, and consumed through its multifandom, multimodal, and affective literacies. According to Felski, genre also becomes deeply connected to knowledge: “all forms of knowing... rely on an array of formal resources, stylistic conventions, and conceptual schemata” (Felski, 87). Web weaving, as a fan practice, helps us know a reader’s affective reception to various media texts; but the meanings inscribed in its fragmentary form also depends on users’ tacit understanding of genre conventions, Tumblr’s curatorial rhythms, and the specific readership for whom these posts carry meaning.

Frieder (2025, 35) examines web weaving as a mode of textual production that is part of Tumblr’s ‘counter-hegemonic’ knowledge structures, where marginalized counterpublics, such as queer and female Tumblr users, determine what cultural texts are relevant and credible. There is no denying that the affective dynamics in these multimodal webs often organize themselves around recurring multivalent themes popular amongst counterpublic fan communities such as queer people, women, and neurodivergent individuals: grief, longing, loneliness, yearning for connection, coming of age, monstrosity, haunted homes, time and memory. They often turn to fandom to process trauma, longing, love, and other ‘feels’ in both fictional fan texts and real-life through web weaving. Themes of haunted houses and monstrosity often embody queer fans’ and women’s experiences of marginalization, forbidden desire, and gender presentation. Longing in queer web weavings mirrors their own social invisibility or desire. Coming-of-age, parental relationships, and loss of time are themes commonly reblogged by young adults. Consequently, many web weaving posts curate media featuring “female, femme, queer, and-of-color subjectivities,” including queer poets such as Mary Oliver, Richard Siken, and Chen Chen, who have become foundational to Tumblr’s literary culture as a ‘peer-blessed’ curriculum of sorts (2025, 41). Rose similarly observes that many users view web weaving as a “counterpoint to formal literary education” that produces a ‘counter-canon’ that speaks to Tumblr’s largely young, queer, female, and people of color demographic (2023, 2).

This brings us to a primary concern in current web weaving scholarship: the relationship between hegemonic knowledge structures and the literary canon within web weaving. The genre often juxtaposes literary elites like Anne Carson, Louise Glück, Richard Siken, Mary Oliver, and Ocean Vuong alongside TV shows such as *Supernatural* and *Hannibal*, and musicians like Hozier and Mitski (Rose 2024). My findings indicate that

Tumblr users widely recognize, and often embrace, this ‘canon’ of writers and artists frequently cited in web weaving (Figure 36). Some users even refer to it as a ‘common literary language’ driven by the demographics of young girls and women (Figure 37). This recognition has created a humorous meta-awareness about how certain quotes and fragments recur across posts, forming an informal yet visible curriculum of Tumblr’s literary favorites (Figure 38). While it is undeniable that Tumblr’s marginalized affective counterpublics developed this recognizable canon, I argue it is not truly ‘counter-hegemonic.’

sorry but they’ve got the richard siken mary oliver franz kafka mitski
 james baldwin lorde ada limón moonlight ocean vuong susan sontag
 brokeback mountain florence and the machine louise glück the
 handmaiden virginia woolf euripides anne carson andrew garfield
 jenny slate phoebe bridgers holly warburton my own private idaho
 oscar wilde folklore the song of achilles egon schiele audre lorde anaïs
 nin frank o’hara félix valloton maurice vladimir nabokov jane austen
 ursula k le guin peter wever howl’s moving castle rainer maria rilke
 sappho emily dickinson charlotte ager fyodor dostoevsky joseph
 lorusso marie howe ilya kaminsky emily brontë dead poets society
 walt whitman donna tartt sandra cisneros leonard cohen wong kar wai
 john keats black sails benjamin alire sáenz john berger jeanette
 winterson salman toor clarice lispector warsan shire sue zhao sufjan
 stevens mahmoud darwish bleachers regina spektor margaret atwood
 disorder. it’s terminal

Figure 36. Literary ‘canons’ in web weaving.

my hot take is that i like all of the “tumblr poets” and i think that the
 common literary language of what is largely girls in their teens and
 twenties on this website is one of the most beautiful things to happen
 to poetry if not literature in a while

Figure 37. Tumblr's 'common literary language'.

yes girl you are so [if i loved you less i might be able to talk about it more] [hands are unbearably beautiful] [i'll take care of you it's rotten work not to me not if it's you] [if you are intolerable let me be the one to tolerate you] [i could recognise him by touch alone] [i love you i want us both to eat well] [on purpose i love you on purpose] [whatever our souls are made of his and mine are the same] [i am half agony half hope] [you have bewitched me body and soul and i love love love you] [he is half of my soul as the poets say] [i'm sick of people saying that love is all a woman is fit for but i'm so lonely] [i love you most ardently] [let me stay tender hearted despite despite despite] [someone has to leave first this is a very old story there is no other version of this story] [mostly i want to be kind] [tell me how all this and love too will ruin us] [you said i killed you haunt me then] [someone somewhere can you understand me a little love me a little] [i will love you as misfortune loves orphans as fire loves innocence and as justice loves to sit and watch while everything goes wrong] [sorry about the blood in your mouth i wish it was mine] [who will come into my kitchen and be hungry for me] can we kiss now

Figure 38. Favourite literary fragments of users

To explain why, I turn to Oumaimas, the user who named the practice and now critiques web weaving as “at best an annoying echo chamber: the same decontextualized quotes and well-liked paintings over and over, each time moving further away from meaning” (Thom, 2022). Another Tumblr user also dramatically posted, “Blocked. And I hope people start web weaving with quotes by your favorite poet taken out of context” (Figure 39). These comments capture anxieties about affective reading within web weaving communities. The critique centers on web weaving’s fragmentation, where quotes become both expressive and estranged. Susan Stewart famously wrote, “The quotation appears as a severed head, a voice whose authority is grounded in itself, and therein lies its power and its limit... It is no longer the possession of its author; it has only the authority of use” (1993, 19). In web weaving, this loss of context through quotation is also both a limitation and a defining feature. Fragments become powerful precisely because they are estranged fragments, mobilized performatively as a fan reading practice to evoke affective intensities of a certain emotion across diverse media texts. But fragmentation turns into an echo chamber of decontextualization when popular fragments from Tumblr’s literary ‘canon’ are endlessly repeated in countless web weaving posts by users who lack meaningful, immersive engagement with the source media texts.

blocked. and i hope people start web weaving with quotes by your favorite poet taken out of context

Figure 39. Growing anxieties around authenticity of reception in web weaving.

Users periodically critique how web weaving’s expressions of affective reception tend to reproduce a narrow, mostly white, middle-class, North American queer subjectivity. Emotions can sometimes feel insincere or performed for belonging within such Tumblr fan communities (Figure 40). Fragments from writers of color like Ocean Vuong, Mitski, and James Baldwin are frequently decontextualized, stripped of their racial, cultural, and historical meanings. (Figures 41.1–41.4). One user highlights how a literary fragment about Vuong’s relationship with her mother is reduced to fit queer romantic relationship arcs in various fandoms, completely decontextualizing its meaning. One can argue this is the fallacy of affective reading often discussed in literary circles not fond of reader-response criticism, I find it more insightful to consider how expressions of affective reception in these reading practices are determined by readers’ interaction with other affective fan readings as well, in turn, they are all influenced by cultural expectations about which emotions hold affective value and gain visibility within platformized fan communities.

Yeah, sorry, we removed the social and racial context from your boyfriend. Yeah, he's being reblogged around tumblr in vague snippets, divorcing the pain of his reality from the profundity of his words. People are tagging him with anime ships and stuff, yeah, I'm sorry, yeah.

Figure 40. Critique of decontextualization in fragmentary reading.

#not as serious a case but Strawberry Blond by mitski
#cuz how are you going to hear an asian american woman talk about feeling like she'll never compare to a light eyed blond and not GET IT

#took an aapi studies class last semester and was shocked to find out that the quote about monsters being beacons and divine #was 1.) from ocean vuong a vietnamese american poet (i had only seen it credited as from on earth we're briefly gorgeous)
 #2.) that the quote was about the characters mother not any sort of love interest (i had only seen it associated with ships)

#james baldwin 🙄
 #god I can't remember the quote I saw that made me drop my jaw (it had been tagged as an attack on titan ship)

#they're weaving him into webs he's being used as a categorical tag
 i'm sorry....

Figures 41.1-41.2. Users frustrated over decontextualization of quotes.

In affective economies, emotions circulate by sticking individual subjects to shared collectives (Ahmed 2004, 19). As Cvetkovich also writes, “Affective expression is coded by class, as much as by categories of race, gender, and sexuality, and middle-class norms often dictate what is deemed appropriate” (2003, 81). In the context of web weaving, this means that certain dominant emotions—like grief, longing, love, girlhood or queerness that are framed within a fairly white, middle-class, North American queer subjectivity in Anglocentric fandoms—gain traction because they resonate widely within these dominant demographics of Tumblr fan communities. These emotions become cultural currencies that users recognize, reproduce, and perform to signal belonging and visibility. Hence, these recurring emotions reinforce and reproduce the dominant cultural norms in this practice, limiting the diversity of affective reception. On Tumblr, this peer pressure is less as overt coercion and more as an affective dynamic, where users internalize community norms of taste, tone, and self-expression that future research should address further. In this context, the endless iteration of fragments from a narrow repertoire of media texts, what some call Tumblr’s ‘counter-hegemonic canon’, can sometimes show a lack of genuine affective engagement with media texts and more a desire to belong in the affective counterpublics of Tumblr where one can perform and archives their fannish feelings to belong to fan communities.

For certain users, web weaving posts become their blog identity, further complicating the sincerity of media reception that emotionally maps fragments together. Although the Tumblr blog is a database of users’ interests and media attachments, many popular web weaving curators have recently begun “solicit[ing] requests for Parallel Posts, as both creative prompt and method to build an audience”, even introducing membership systems to monetize their curatorial labour (Rose 2025, 112). Although the sums they receive are nominal, this often creates parasocial pressure through their followers, undoubtedly complicating the authenticity of media engagement. As a result, curators may begin to perform or amplify fragments of particular themes, texts, fandoms, or characters that are known to resonate with their audience or hold wider appeal. In such instances, the commodification of affective reception sweeps users who take pride in occupying a counter-hegemonic fan space into the value-production logics of platform capitalism because the affective reading and reception of fans becomes a site for monetization. For these reasons, I refuse to claim that knowledge organized, produced and consumed through web weaving is counter-hegemonic. Yet, it cannot be denied that by bringing disconnected media fragments into intertextual dialogue with one another, this practice encourages readers to curate webs of

feelings rooted in deeply felt reading experiences. Whether the ‘feels’ are deeply personal or carefully performed in the regime of affective fandom economies under platform capitalism, they accumulate into a shared affective archive that defines Tumblr.

Conclusion

The reader is the space on which all the quotations that make up a writing are inscribed without any of them being lost — Roland Barthes (1986)

This thesis opened with Dubravka Ugrešić’s speculative vision of a future where Literature (with a capital L) survives only as fragments of media texts scattered in “literary web sites” across cyberspace. It is a snapshot of digital reading today: fragmented, non-linear, and platformized due to the overabundance of media texts in a hyperconnected digital world. The platformization of fan communities and fragmentary fan reading practices have made this cultural shift in digital reading culture blatantly clear. Hence, this thesis turns to one such fragmentary fan reading practice called web weaving that has spread across fan communities on the digital platform of Tumblr. A platform that currently remains understudied due to Tumblr’s cultural decline both on the Internet and in scholarship. Through this case study, I consider what it means to be a reader in a hyperconnected yet fragmented digital world increasingly characterized by the platformization of fan culture.

Guided by this question, I look into how Tumblr’s sociotechnical infrastructure and its culture of ‘feels’ have established Tumblr as an affective archive in the eyes of users. The rise of web weaving as a transformative fan reading practice is an extension of Tumblr culture’s archival and affective impulses, as it curates fragmentary media texts based on the ‘feels’ or deeply felt reading experiences of Tumblr users. The conceptual metaphor of ‘feels’ captures how private media reception becomes public expression in Tumblr’s affective fandom economies, where individual emotions ‘stick’ to shared media interests and create a shared terrain of affinities that coalesces users into fan communities. The circulation and performance of these ‘feels’ is mediated by users’ perceptions of platform affordances and constraints, along with broader cultural norms known as the ‘platform vernacular’. The analysis of Tumblr’s most significant affordances such as high pseudonymity, high multimodality, low searchability, high non-linear temporality, low algorithmic governance and high interactivity, all made possible due to Tumblr’s reblogging, tagging, pseudonymous design and the multimodal communicative work they do demonstrates the balance Tumblr strikes in granting a public yet private space for users. It reveals how users treat their blogs as intimate databases, carefully curating their passions, obsessions, and media interests. Tumblr thus functions as what Cvetkovich terms an ‘archive of feelings,’ preserving traces of emotion evoked by media texts within a networked digital community of fans.

Although Tumblr hosts affective ‘counterpublics’ such as queer and female fans who value the quintessential Tumblr culture of interpretive fan practices, Tumblr still cannot be fully considered as a ‘counter-hegemonic’ space as opposed to the perspectives of users and certain scholars. Tumblr still operates under platform capitalism, and emotions become cultural currencies that users recognize, reproduce and perform to signal belonging and

visibility in digital fan communities. Despite the platform's decline in mainstream attention and struggles with monetization, Tumblr remains afloat due to these affective engagements and also continues to introduce new features aimed at monetizing user presence, attention, and affective interactions with fan content. Yet, limited automation and user resistance to algorithmic governance have slowed the data extractivism typical of platform capitalism.

In this anomalous platform environment that functions as an archival space, I have demonstrated that web weaving is both a symptom and a contagion of how we read in the fragmented and platformized digital age. The term “web” itself carries a double meaning, referring both to the networked sociotechnical infrastructure of digital platforms and the act of weaving fragments into meanings. Through web weaving, readers immerse themselves in a mode of recognition where each user sees themselves within a tapestry of fragmented media texts and simultaneously witnesses others seeing themselves reflected in this woven tapestry. Recognition extends beyond seeing yourself in a text to seeing yourself as a networked self. Each user incorporates their own interpretive experiences into a web weaving post, which is then shared, reinterpreted and shared again—and so it continues, creating a networked self. Web weaving also embodies an aesthetic reading experience of enchantment by immersing readers in a fragmentary, intertextual mosaic of meanings, forging a poetic identity as Tumblr users build their blogs into networks of instantaneous experiences where impressions, images, and sounds converge to express their affective intensities.

The study of web weaving offers a window to witness the transformation of readers into archivists who preserve that which makes them feel seen, enchanted, and helps them gain knowledge about the sprawling sociality of Tumblr fan culture and the kind of media texts and emotional responses towards media fan communities revere and glorify. This has led to a repeated decontextualization of fragments in web weaving posts, drawn from this relatively narrow set of media texts that users and certain scholars call Tumblr's ‘canon’. As a result, the web weaving practice sometimes signals less authentic affective engagement with the media and more a desire to belong within these fan communities. The endless reproduction of similar emotions and media texts in web weaving brings into focus the ‘value-added’ logic of capitalism. It inevitably reproduces cultural norms as a paradigm of predominantly white, middle-class, North American queer subjectivities. The reader, as an archivist, inhabits a liminal space between preservation and curatorial performance, where every act of preserving vignettes of media reception is itself part of an exhibition.

The multimodal and fragmentary nature of web weaving warranted a deeper exploration of the rise of such contemporary fan reading practices, yet this study has just begun to scratch the surface. To conclude, I would like to discuss the evolution of web weaving beyond Tumblr alongside the limitations of this study that potential avenues of research should address.

Future research should continue to address the fragmentary, collage-like ethos of web weaving, situating it within the broader lineage of fragmentary fan practices on Tumblr. To fully grasp web weaving as a climactic expression of Tumblr's symbiotic relationship between its platform infrastructure and user culture, one that thrives on multimodal and fragmentary fan activities, also demands more in-depth comparative analysis. For example, a close comparison between web weaving posts and fandom textpost memes could reveal distinctive curatorial expressions emerging from the juxtaposition of media texts on Tumblr, shedding light on how these forms represent interpretive reading experiences.

Web weaving is a practice observed across various fandoms on Tumblr. However, despite its ubiquity, most media fragments involved are closely linked to Tumblr's established 'literary canon' of recurring works and themes that I previously discussed. A focused investigation into specific fan communities could illuminate how these fragments and canonical themes are interpreted and repurposed, exploring the function of this canon as a form of memory work within Tumblr's platformized fan culture. Such research could also benefit from an ethnographic approach, including participant observations through interviews with users about their experiences of creating and engaging with web weaving. This would help uncover how factors like race, class, queer identities, and linguistic diversity in global south fandoms imagine or reimagine this practice, offering a richer understanding of the variegated reading experiences that both reflect and respond to the fragmented and platformized nature of web weaving.

Beyond Tumblr, the rise of web weaving on TikTok as 'web weaving slideshows' and on Instagram as 'quote dumps' presents a significant avenue for scholarly inquiry. On TikTok, snippets of poetry, quotes, film stills, and paintings appear in sequence, often accompanied by background music that harmonizes with the theme of the weaving. 'Quote dumps' on Instagram are often plagiarized from Tumblr's web weaving, taking the form of carousel posts featuring multiple fragments in a sequential post format. Many Tumblr users have expressed distaste for the adaptive migration of web weaving on these platforms, viewing them as a dilution of the original practice into vague moodboards (Figures 42.1-42.2). While recent articles praise web weaving's ability to express inexpressible emotional states through literary fragments and bring tenderness to otherwise monotonous social feeds on TikTok (Quin 2023), such preliminary accounts overlook what platformization and fragmentation have done to literature in a hyperconnected digital world. How do the infrastructures and cultures of these platforms influence the multimodal adaptations of web weaving? Instagram's visual-heavy affordances, combined with user conventions around screenshotting, reposting, and creative curation, contrast sharply with TikTok's highly algorithm-driven, audiovisual ecosystem. Understanding these dynamics would deepen our grasp of web weaving's evolution across platforms and illuminate the broader implications for fragmentary practices within platformized reading cultures.

#people have been reposting them on tiktok with gentle little guitar bits
 #and if possible it makes me even more feral

sometimes web weaving on instagram and tiktok is just like a vague moodboard of something they don't even add the caption and sources in the end and the format is just not it i hate it so much

Figures 42.1-42.2. Users distaste for rise of web weaving on Instagram and TikTok

The emergence of web weaving also invites a broader study into how ‘curation’ itself is becoming a key concept that can help us codify cultures of platform capitalism. In many social media cultural research projects centering digital fandom, the excitement around new curatorial and creative practices, particularly their multimodal, expressive potential, often eclipses a critical engagement with the underlying platform structures that harness curation as a mode of value extraction. These platforms convert ‘free user labor’ and affective engagement into commodified assets. This research aims to complicate such a “black box” view of platforms by engaging with what platforms enable for users as well as how and why. However, the multimodal, affective-discursive methodologies employed in this study, combined with Tumblr’s pseudonymous userbase, may not fully capture the shortfalls of Tumblr as a platform that users continue to perceive as ‘counter-hegemonic’ because it is not complicit in the corporate platform complex in the same way as Meta, Facebook, and TikTok. The implicit but pervasive agency of social ‘peer pressure’ in users’ affective engagements within platform cultures, especially in the context of seemingly subversive fan spaces, can also be an interesting direction for future research.

Despite these limitations, this thesis offers a nuanced analysis of the evolving identity of the reader, an underlying question that often remains implicit in much of the scholarship on digital reading culture. Web weaving might not provide a complete answer, but it shows that to be a reader today means gathering scattered threads from multimodal textual worlds; weaving intertextual connections that traverse highbrows and lowbrows of culture; to linger within the fraught space between sincerity and performativity in reading experiences; and to archive the self through a polyphonic chorus of others.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths: This thesis presents an exploratory study of web weaving as a fragmentary and multimodal fan reading practice. It not only renews scholarly attention on Tumblr, a platform whose unique culture has seen limited rigorous study since 2018, but also fills a crucial gap in research on the ‘affective turn’ within fan studies and digital reading culture. It presents a clear analytical framework with extensive scholarly sources that supports a comprehensive understanding of the topic. The ‘methodological bricolage’ approach is a strong point of this work, aligning well with the fragmented nature of web weaving and platformized fan engagement. This approach also illuminates how affect can be critically examined within fan discourse, supported by a strong theoretical foundation. The use of user-generated content, such as meta-Tumblr posts and visual examples of web weaving, serves as effective primary material that not only clarifies the concept but also sheds light on user perspectives on Tumblr’s affordances and vernacular practices, complementing secondary literature. The theorization of Tumblr as an ‘archive of feelings’ is a distinct contribution to the study of Tumblr as a platform. Finally, the application of Felski’s modes of textual engagement to closely read web weaving enriches the robustness and depth of contemporary reading practices in digital culture that blur the lines between affect and critique.

Weaknesses: Since the focus is primarily on Tumblr’s web weaving, it limits the broader applicability of the research question to effectively understand how fragmentation and platformization impact other reading practices on social media platforms. Lack of extensive ethnographic or interview data constrains understanding of user motivations, experiences, and demographic nuances. The study could benefit from a more comparative analysis of fan reading practices on Tumblr to understand the social curation activities on Tumblr that contribute to its archival space. The critique of platform capitalism could have been more rigorous had it been studied from a broader platform economy perspective, incorporating how power, labour, and monetization operate within Tumblr’s platform architecture. Tumblr’s pseudonymous userbase also might skew findings toward more engaged communities, missing marginal or less visible fan practices that are not necessarily Anglophonic. As a result, the reliance on the selection of the dataset introduces a possibility of bias, thus expanding data collection efforts could provide a more comprehensive view of the practice.

Opportunities: The conclusion provides an overview of future directions this study can take. It basically suggests studying the fragmentary form of web weaving within Tumblr’s lineage of fragmentary fan practices to uncover insights into interpretive fan culture. Investigating the practice through the lens of specific fan communities using digital ethnographic sensibilities would illuminate how Tumblr’s literary ‘canon’ functions as

memory work on Tumblr. Beyond Tumblr, examining web weaving's adaptations on TikTok ('web weaving slideshows') and Instagram ('quote dumps') offers critical insight into how platform infrastructures with their distinct cultures have adapted this practice. The study also encourages a formal analysis of web weaving and the poetic identity forged in the user base. Finally, this research opens avenues to critically study how 'curation' operates as a mode of value extraction within platform capitalism, urging deeper engagement with the platform economies underpinning these digital fan cultures, which remain underexplored despite the excitement around creative practices.

Threats: Tumblr's ambiguous position as a declining platform poses a risk to the longevity and contemporary relevance of research centered on it. The rapid pace of change in social media trends and fan practices means some observations may quickly become outdated or require ongoing research. This project deliberately avoids quantitative computational methods, given the fragmentary and affective nature of the subject, but the concept of 'affect' carries varied and sometimes contested meanings across disciplines, which may complicate how this research is received. Additionally, shifts in ownership, business models, or platform policies can abruptly reshape platform dynamics, potentially impacting fan practices and the applicability of these findings.

Bibliography

Adriaansen, Robbert-Jan. 2022. "Dark Academia: Curating Affective History in a COVID-Era Internet Aesthetic." *International Public History* 5 (2): 105–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/iph-2022-2047>

Ahmed, Sara. 2004. "Affective Economies." *Social Text* 22, no. 2: 117-139.
<https://muse.jhu.edu/article/55780>.

Alberto, Maria. 2021. "EXPLORING HOW FANS USE PLATFORMS: A Platform Studies Approach to Fan Studies Projects". *A Fan Studies Primer: Method, Research, Ethics*. Edited by Paul Booth and Rebecca Williams. Fandom and Culture Series. Chicago: University of Iowa Press.

Anderson, Benedict R. O’G. 1983. *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London New York: Verso.

Baetens, Jan, and Jan Van Looy. 2007. "Digitising Cultural Heritage: The Role of Interpretation in Cultural Preservation". *Image [&] Narrative*: 17.

Barthes, Roland. "Death of the Author." *The Rustle of Language*. Translated by Richard Howard. 1986, pp 49-55

Berg, Anna & von Scheve, Christian & Ural, N. & Walter-Jochum, Robert. 2019. "Reading for Affect – a Methodological Proposal for Analyzing Affective Dynamics in Discourse". *Analyzing Affective Societies: Methods and Methodologies*. 1st ed. Edited by Antje Kahl. Routledge, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429424366>.

Birke, Dorothee, and Johannes Fehrle. 2019. "#booklove: How Reading Culture Is Adapted on the Internet." *Komparatistik Online*: 60–86.

Birke, Dorothee. 2021. "Social Reading? On the Rise of a ‘Bookish’ Reading Culture Online." *Poetics Today* 42, no. 2: 149–72. <https://doi.org/10.1215/03335372-8883178>.

Booten, K. P. 2017. *A Library of Fragments: Digital Quotations, New Literacies, and Attention on Social Media*. UC Berkeley. ProQuest ID: Booten_berkeley_0028E_16955. Merritt ID: ark:/13030/m5838mt4. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7nj2j0jb>

Booth, Paul. 2015. *Playing Fans: Negotiating Fandom and Media in the Digital Age*. Iowa City: University Of Iowa Press.

- Booth, Paul. 2017. *Digital Fandom 2.0: New Media Studies*. Second Edition, Revised ed. Digital Formations 114. New York: Peter Lang Inc., International Academic Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.3726/978-1-4539-1654-4>.
- Bouchardon, Serge. 2019. “Mind the Gap! 10 Gaps for Digital Literature?” *Electronic Book Review*. <https://electronicbookreview.com/essay/mind-the-gap-10-gaps-for-digital-literature/>.
- Brett, Ingrid, and Sarah Maslen. 2021. “Stage Whispering: Tumblr Hashtags Beyond Categorization.” *Social Media + Society* 7 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051211032138>.
- Brubaker, Rogers. 2023. *Hyperconnectivity and Its Discontents*. Cambridge Hoboken (N.J.): Polity Press.
- Bullard, Julia. 2018. *Curated Folksonomies : Three Implementations of Structure through Human Judgment*. Version 1. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.14288/1.0387156>.
- Busse, Kristina. 2017. “The ethics of studying online fandom”. Edited by Scott, Suzanne, and Melissa A. Click. *The Routledge Companion to Media Fandom*. New York ; London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group: 7-17
- Busse, Kristina and Karen Hellekson. 2006. “Introduction: Work in Progress.” *Fan Fiction and Fan Communities in the Age of the Internet*, edited by Kristina Busse and Karen Hellekson. McFarland & Company, Inc.
- Chew, Natalie. 2018. “Tumblr as Counterpublic Space for Fan Mobilization.” *Transformative Works and Cultures* 27. <https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2018.1186>.
- Cho, Alexander. 2015. “Queer Reverb: Tumblr, Affect, Time.” In *Networked Affect*, edited by Ken Hillis, Susanna Paasonen, and Michael Petit, 43–58. The MIT Press, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9715.003.0005>.
- Cho, Alexander. 2022. “Queerness, Race, and Affect on “Peak Tumblr””. *The Routledge Companion to Gender and Affect*: 268-279.
- Collins, Jim. 2010. *Bring on the Books for Everybody*. Duke University Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822391975>.
- Cvetkovich, Ann. 2003. *An Archive of Feelings: Trauma, Sexuality, and Lesbian Public Cultures*. Series Q. Durham London: Duke University Press.

Dahlberg-Dodd, Hannah E. 2019. “The Author in the Postinternet Age: Fan works, authorial function, and the archive.” *Transformative Works and Cultures*, no. 30.
<https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2019.1408>.

De Certeau, Michel. 1984. *The practice of everyday life*. Minneapolis, MN: U of Minnesota Press.

De Kosnik, Abigail. 2013. “Fandom as Free Labour.” *Digital Labor: The Internet as Playground and Factory*. Edited by Trebor Scholz. New York: Routledge.

De Kosnik, Abigail. 2016. *Rogue Archives: Digital Cultural Memory and Media Fandom*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Derrida, Jacques, and Eric Prenowitz. 1995. “Archive Fever: A Freudian Impression.” *Diacritics* 25, no. 2: 9–63. <https://doi.org/10.2307/465144>.

Domingo, M., Kress, G., O’Connell, R., Elliott, H., Squire, C., Jewitt, C., & Adami, E. 2014. Development of methodologies for researching online: The case of food blogs. National Centre for Research Methods Working Paper, 11(14).

Eichhorn, Kate. 2008. "Archival Genres: Gathering Texts and Reading Spaces." *Invisible Culture* 12:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.47761/494a02f6.93f3f522>.

Eichhorn, Kate. 2008. “Archival Genres: Gathering Texts and Reading Spaces.” *Invisible Culture* 12:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.47761/494a02f6.93f3f522>.

Felski, Rita. 2008. *Uses of Literature*. 1st ed. Wiley-Blackwell Manifestos Ser, v. 71. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.

Freider, Ester. 2021 “CALLING ALL TUMBLRINAS: Hito Steyerl’s Conception of the ‘Poor Image’ and Communal Online Reworking of Culture Amongst Tumblr Girls,” https://www.academia.edu/91532944/CALLING_ALL_TUMBLRINAS_Hito_Steyerl_s_Conception_of_the_Poor_Image_and_Communal_Online_Reworking_of_Culture_Amongst_Tumblr_Girls.

Freider, Ester. 2025. *I’m like a Pdf but a Girl: Girlblogging as a Nomadic Pedagogy*. Femme Social Press.

Gledhill, Evan Hayles. 2018. “Tumblr and the Romantic Sentiment Album: Bricolage and the Culture of the Margins.” *Transformative Works and Cultures*, no. 27. <https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2018.1213>.

Gomart, Emilie & Antoine Hennion. 1999 “A Sociology of Attachment: Music Amateurs, Drug Users.” *The Sociological Review* 47.1: 220–247.

Gowrley, Freya. 2024. *Fragmentary Forms: A New History of Collage*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Greimas, Algirdas Julien, and Jacques Fontanille. 1993. *The Semiotics of Passions: From States of Affairs to States of Feeling*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Grossberg, Lawrence. 1992. “Is There a Fan in the House? The Affective Sensibility of Fandom.” *The Adoring Audience: Fan Culture and Popular Media*. edited by Lisa Lewis. New York: Routledge.

Hautsch, Jessica. 2022. “Pic Sets, Fan Cognition, and Fannish Networks of Meaning.” *Transformative Works and Cultures* 38. <https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2022.2151>.

Hayles NK. 2007. “Narrative and database: natural symbionts”. *PMLA/Publications of the Modern Language Association of America*. 122(5): 1603–1608.

Hoover, Amanda. 2025. “Gen Z Is Flocking to the One Social Media Platform Millennials Didn’t Ruin.” *Business Insider*. <https://www.businessinsider.com/gen-z-flocking-tumblr-millennials-musk-zuckerberg-safe-space-2025-4>.

Jenkins, Henry. 1992. *Textual Poachers: Television Fans & Participatory Culture*. Reprint. Studies in Culture and Communication. New York, NY: Routledge.

Jenkins, Henry. 2019. “Fan Materiality and Affect: Interview with Nicolle Lamerichs (Part 2) — Pop Junctions.” <http://henryjenkins.org/blog/2019/9/8/interview-with-nicholle-lamerichs-part-2-erjjs>.

Jewitt, Carey, ed. 2009. *The Routledge Handbook of Multimodal Analysis*. London ; New York: Routledge.

Lamerichs, Nicolle, and Nieves Rosendo. 2022. “Affect and the Analysis of Transmedial Characters.” *Narrative* 30 (2): 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1353/nar.2022.0011>.

Lamerichs, Nicolle. 2020. *Productive Fandom: Intermediality and Affective Reception in Fan Cultures*. Transmedia: Participatory Culture and Media Convergence 4. Baltimore, Maryland: Project Muse.

Lindgren, Simon. 2017. *Digital Media & Society*. Los Angeles: Sage.

Lowe, J.S.A. “Kitten Thinks of Nothing but Murder All Day: Tumblr Text Post Memes as Fandom Détournement.” 2020. *a tumblr book: platforms and cultures*. Edited by Allison McCracken, Alexander Cho, Louisa Stein, Indira Neil Hoch. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

Mandolessi, Silvana. 2023. “The digital turn in memory studies.” *Memory Studies*, 16(6), 1513-1528. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17506980231204201>

Manovich, Lev. 2001. *The Language of New Media*.
http://dss-edit.com/plu/Manovich-Lev_The_Language_of_the_New_Media.pdf.

Massumi, Brian. 2002. *Parables for the Virtual: Movement, Affect, Sensation*. Durham: Duke Univ. Press.

Mayer, Ariane and Serge Bouchardon. 2020. “The Digital Subject: From Narrative Identity to Poetic Identity?” *Electronic Book Review*. <https://doi.org/10.7273/53th-r785>

McCracken, Allison, Alexander Cho, Louisa Stein, and Indira Hoch. 2020. *a tumblr book: platform and cultures*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

Minkel, Elizabeth. 2023. “Tumblr Is Always Dying”. *Wired*.
<https://www.wired.com/story/end-of-the-tumblr-era/>.

Mithen. 2014. “In Defense of Feels” *Fanlore*. https://fanlore.org/wiki/In_Defense_of_Feels

Nieborg, D. B., & Poell, T. 2018. The platformization of cultural production: Theorizing the contingent cultural commodity. *New Media & Society*, 20(11), 4275–4292.
 doi:10.1177/1461444818769694

obsession_inc. “Transformational Fandom.” *Fanlore*.
https://fanlore.org/wiki/Transformational_Fandom

oumaima. 2019. “My Year of Practicing Tenderness.” Medium (blog). May 20, 2019. <https://summerfruit.medium.com/my-year-of-practicing-tenderness-47366dd2a3e3>.

Oz, Mustafa, Saif Shahin, and Scott B. Greeves. 2023. “Platform Affordances and Spiral of Silence: How Perceived Differences between Facebook and Twitter Influence Opinion Expression Online.” *Technology in Society* 76:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102431>.

Papacharissi, Zizi A. 2018. *A Networked Self and Platforms, Stories, Connections*. New York, NY: Routledge.

Poell, T., Nieborg, D., & van Dijck, J. 2019. Platformisation. *Internet Policy Review*, 8(4), 1–13. doi:10.14763/2019.4.1425

Popova, Milena. 2017. “Slight dub-con but they both wanted it hardcore: Erotic fanfiction as a form of cultural activism around sexual consent.” Doctoral dissertation. University of the West of England.

Pressman, Jessica. 2020. *Bookishness: Loving Books in a Digital Age*. Columbia University

Quin, Emma. 2023. “TikTok Quote Dumps: The Girlies Are Web Weaving Again.” *Polyester Zine*.

<https://www.polyesterzine.com/features/tiktok-quote-dumps-web-weaving>](<https://www.polyesterzine.com/features/tiktok-quote-dumps-web-weaving>

Rose, Axel-Nathaniel. 2023. “Parallel Posts, Tumblr, and the Necessity of Poetry in the Digital Age: ‘You Are Starved for It and You Don’t Even Realise You’re Hungry.’” *Axon: Creative Explorations* 13 (2): 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.54375/001/upj4lq3ogc>.

Rose, Axel-Nathaniel. 2024. “#web-weaving: Parallel Posts, Commonplace Books, and Networked Technologies of the Self on Tumblr.” In “Fandom and Platforms,” edited by Maria K. Alberto, Effie Sapuridis, and Lesley Willard, special issue, *Transformative Works and Cultures*, no. 42. <https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2024.2495>.

Rose, Axel-Nathaniel. 2025. “#parallels: Web Weaving, Media Fandom, and the Role of Bookishness on Tumblr and Equinox; or, the Spirit of the Age.” UNSW Sydney.. <https://doi.org/10.26190/UNSWORKS/30845>.

Sedgwick, Eve Kosofsky. 1997. “Paranoid Reading and Reparative Reading; or, You’re So Paranoid, You Probably Think This Introduction Is About You EVE KOSOFSKY SEDGWICK.” In *Novel Gazing*, edited by Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, Duke University Press:1–38.. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822382478-001>

Snelson, Daniel Scott. 2025. *The Little Database: A Poetics of Media Formats*. Electronic Mediations 64. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Sobchack, Vivian. 2004. *Carnal Thoughts: Embodiment and Moving Image Culture*. Berkeley: Univ. of California Press.

Stein, Louisa, and Kristina Busse. 2009. "Limit Play: Fan Authorship between Source Text, Intertext, and Context." *Popular Communication* 7 (4): 192–207.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15405700903177545>.

Stein, Louisa Ellen. 2015. *Millennial Fandom: Television Audiences in the Transmedia Age*. Iowa City: University of Iowa Press.

Stein, Louisa Ellen. 2017. "Tumblr Fan Aesthetics." In *The Routledge Companion to Media Fandom*, edited by Melissa A. Click and Suzanne Scott, 86–97. Abingdon: Routledge.

Stewart, Susan. *On Longing: Narratives of the Miniature, the Gigantic, the Souvenir, the Collection*. Duke University Press, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1220n8g>.

Stynze Gómez, Harly Onelly, and Erika De Los Ángeles Velásquez Vallecillo. 2021. "Fragmented Reading: A Strategy Learning in Digital Era". *Revista Torreón Universitario* 10 (27): 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.5377/torreon.v10i27.10837>.

Terranova, Tiziana. 2000. "Free Labor: Producing Culture for the Digital Economy." *Social Text* 18, no. 2: 33-58. <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/31873>.

Terranova, Tiziana. 2022. *After the Internet: Digital Networks between Capital and the Common*. Semiotext(e) Intervention Series 33. South Pasadena, CA: Semiotext(e)

Thom, Alessandra. 2022. "(ARCHIVE FEVER) Web Weaving, by Alessandra Thom." SPAM Zine. <https://www.spamzine.co.uk/post/archive-fever-web-weaving-by-alessandra-thom>.

Tiidenberg, Katrin, Natalie Ann Hendry, and Crystal Abidin. 2021. *Tumblr*. Cambridge: Polity.

Ugrešić, Dubravka. "Homepage". <https://www.dubravkaugresic.com/>

Vist, Elise, Milena Popova, and Julia E. Largent. 2021. "What Does Fan Studies Feel Like". *A Fan Studies Primer: Method, Research, Ethics*. Edited by Paul Booth and Rebecca Williams. Fandom and Culture Series. Chicago: University of Iowa Press.

Walker, Rob. 2012. “Can Tumblr’s David Karp Embrace Ads Without Selling Out?”
 Magazine. *The New York Times*.
<https://www.nytimes.com/2012/07/15/magazine/can-tumblrs-david-karp-embrace-ads-without-selling-out.html>.

Wiki, Contributors to Aesthetics. n.d. “Internet Aesthetics.” Aesthetics Wiki.
https://aesthetics.fandom.com/wiki/Category:Internet_Aesthetics.

Westberg, Gustav. 2021. “Affect as a Multimodal Practice.” *Multimodality & Society* 1 (1):
 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2634979521992734>.